

Innovative Governance Model

DELIVERABLE 2.6 – FIRST ELEMENTS

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents an option for an **innovative model for food system governance for sustainability**, based on insights gained from various studies and activities realised.

First, a systematic literature review of existing governance models of food systems, that are striving to reach sustainability, has been performed. The main findings are here presented like definitions of FS governance, key sustainability issues published, current barriers and proposed solutions for food system governance for sustainability, and implications for new sustainable governance models. The major outcome is a **new definition** for food system governance for sustainability as: *'the continuous process of orchestration of policies and (multiple) food systems consisting of diverse interacting actors, respecting (in)formal rules and striving to provide food for all, in equitable and environmentally-friendly ways, at any time and in any context'* and an innovative governance model (Donner, Mamès, de Vries., 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>; [Figure in chapter 6](#)).

Secondly, an overview of existing **governance architectures** of running partnerships has been made followed by an analysis and description of common features of these architectures. This resulted in a draft governance architecture for an ideal European Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (P-SFS).

Third, **four in-depth case studies** have been performed, to get insights into governance, tools, and roles of actors in food systems. Some main findings are (i) each kind of partner (private SMEs/groups, research, public, NGOs...) is preferably equally represented at higher decision levels; (ii) The decision process is proposed to be transparent, robust, and irrevocable (for example using democratic voting systems), (iii) intermediaries play crucial roles in the functioning of partnerships, (iv) horizontal governance 'organs' are suggested above hierarchic ones, (v) a role of next generations in governance mechanisms is recommended.

Fourth, lessons learned from **Mirror Group** events, strongly suggest taking into account vulnerable and less visible FS actors in future Partnerships.

Fifth, a **workshop on governance and scenarios**, with all actor groups within FOODPathS, reveals that different actor groups may fit differently into scenarios. Such an exercise allows for the alignment of fair positionings of actors in a variety of future governance models already at the start of establishing partnerships.

Finally, all **findings are cross-checked with an innovative governance model** proposed in the scientific article mentioned above. It can be concluded that this model covers major aspects of food system governance for sustainability as found in FOODPathS studies. One striking observation is the **importance of orchestration of and by all FS actors active in multiple, interacting food systems or FS partnerships**. It may be seen as a form of **self-organization** like in complex adaptive systems in ecology, within clear boundaries and playing fields. A useful metaphor is a music orchestra: all musicians should individually play harmonically to get an overall harmonic output. If one plays out-of-tune, the overall sound is not harmonic (de Vries et al., 2021). But to play harmonic asks more than just individually playing harmonic. It needs to take into account e.g. the music hall conditions, the synchronization between musicians, or the differences between musicians and their instruments.

2. Introduction

Current environmental, social, and economic challenges are overwhelming (SAPEA, 2019; SCAR, 2023). They nearly show all (linear or exponential) growth curves, sooner or later leading to an overheated planet or chaos (Prigogine and Stenger, 1985; de Vries et al., 2018). Hence, global citizens together should change food systems such that their output endlessly balances between planetary and societal limits (sometimes called safe operating spaces (Anderies et al., 2019)). This is schematically presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. FS outputs: from growth patterns towards balancing curves between planetary and societal limits (retrieved from <https://www.foodpaths.eu/resource/the-eu-partnership-sfs-in-international-context/>; <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-04454434>; de Vries et al., 2021)

Hence, the self-organization (Kauffman, 1995) or jointly harmonic orchestration of *and by* all FS actors is becoming urgent and crucial to reach sustainably evolving food systems. This directly implies another view on governance. Since FOODPathS aims to design a prototype for the future Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Partnership in Europe, governance is a priority topic, next to other topics like co-funding strategies, *Modus Operandi*, a sustainability charter, a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), and a series of co-creation cases, among others.

Potential trade-offs of proposed activities, including effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation (C&D&E) strategies – resulting from the efforts of involving local and global stakeholders in shaping the future Partnership – will be primordial to be pursued.

To achieve this change from a governance perspective, our main question is ‘**do we need an innovative model for food system governance for sustainability?**’ Therefore a review of the literature and existing governance architectures, in-depth case studies, mirror groups, and scenarios have been performed and analyzed.

3. Objectives of the Deliverable and Methodologies applied

The main objective of this plan is to offer the future Partnership Consortium an innovative governance model that helps its guidance of all activities carried out by the Partnership.

For doing so, several sub-objectives have been defined and carried out following various methodologies and actions.

	Objectives	Methodologies / main actions
1.	To analyze the current state-of-the-art research on food system governance for sustainability and to understand current barriers and potential solutions.	A systematic literature review on food system governance linked to sustainability.
2.	To get to know current empirical examples of large partnerships.	Review on governance architectures from existing Partnerships and 'large initiatives'
3.	To get a general picture of existing cases of co-creating partnerships in different countries, to understand more in-depth governance mechanisms contributing to sustainability in food systems.	Collection of 50+ cases, followed by four in-depth case studies
4.	From insights obtained in FOODPathS towards a first image of the Governance Model	Cross-checking findings with an innovative governance model AND finalizing & reporting the Deliverable
NEXT STEPS in 2025		
5.	Utilizing the Innovative Governance Model	Discussion with experts in & outside FOODPathS, all WPs
6.	Introducing the Innovative Governance Model in the final Manual of the Prototype Partners	WP2 team

Table 1 - Objectives and main actions implemented

4. Target audience

Target audiences are:

- Future Partnerships like FutureFoodS, PRIMA-MED, and any other large partnership-like initiatives (for example as represented in the Advisory Board of FOODPathS, and in networks of FOODPathS partners.
- The EC DG RTD and the SCAR SWG FS are guiding partnerships and seek to establish connections between partnerships.
- All actors who are – or will be – involved in future Partnerships and seeking fair and balanced interactions to reach sustainable outcomes together with other food system actors from public, private, philanthropic, academic, non-governmental, and civil society sectors.

5. Activities and Results

5.1. Review of governance models from scientific literature

5.1.1. Context and objective

The literature review aimed to understand how food system governance is linked to and can contribute to sustainability (Donner, Mamès, de Vries, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>). The term governance probably originates from the Greek word *kybernan*, in Latin later *gubernare*, which means to steer, pilot, or direct (Levi-Faur, 2012). Governance in general is defined as “the act or process of governing or overseeing the control and direction of something (such as a country or an organization)”¹. In academic literature, governance is a broad and not consistently-defined concept, applied in political, management, economic, social, and spatial sciences. It has its roots in the management and business studies on corporate governance, where it has largely been explored (Tricker, 2015; Ruhanen et al., 2010). Food governance refers to processes and actor configurations that frame decision-making and encompass food production, distribution, and consumption activities (van Bers et al. 2016). Governance of food systems in the context of sustainability is an interesting field of research but emerged only more recently.

5.1.2. Methodology

To analyze the current state-of-the-art research on food system governance for sustainability and to understand which models and principles of food system governance can contribute to sustainability, a systematic literature review was carried out. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) method was applied and resulted in the selection of 34 articles, published in mostly thematic and interdisciplinary journals between 2015 and January 2024. The analysis of these articles included food system governance definitions, sustainability issues, and current barriers in FS governance for sustainability as well as potential solutions.

5.1.3. Results

Result 1 – Food system governance definitions found in the reviewed literature.

Reference	Definition of Food System Governance
Arthur et al. (2022)	“Understanding FS governance requires an analysis of actors, their relationships, and how they impact the food system.”
Carrad et al. (2022)	“formal and informal rules, norms and processes that shape policies and decisions that affect food systems (HLPE, 2020).”
Chen et al. (2021)	“the interplay between food system (or food chain) actors in decision-making processes that shape food systems and their development. Governance in this sense is the way rules, norms, and actions are structured, sustained, regulated and implemented.”

¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/governance>

del Valle et al. (2022)	“formal and informal interactions between institutions and people to enable the environment in which food systems perform (Candel, 2014; Kennedy et al., 2017; Béné et al., 2019).”
Hammelman et al. (2020)	“the establishment of rules, practices, and processes that structure the flows of power and control in the food system (Jessop, 1998; Kennedy & Liljeblad, 2016).”
Levkoe et al. (2023)	“Governance involves both explicit rules and implicit practices, customs, and assumptions related to who and what is considered part of a food system, who should be included in governance decisions, and in what ways.”
van Bers et al. (2019)	“processes and actor constellations that shape decision-making and activities related to the production, distribution, and consumption of food (van Bers et al., 2016).”

From these definitions, three recurrent key elements of food system governance can be identified, which will be discussed below.

- (i) the importance of actors, their relations and interactions (at a system level, horizontal and vertical),
- (ii) the control, power balances, and decision-making,
- (iii) the formal and informal rules, norms, and practices.

Result 2 – sustainability issues

The conditions and needs for achieving sustainability

Several authors reflect on a change in current values to enable sustainable food system governance. For example, governments should prioritize key goals such as the right to food and sustainability over corporate profits (Clapp et al., 2021); governance models should be established that allow people to govern their food based on their principles and values (del Valle et al., 2022); and values, interests, and behaviors of many different food system actors need to be re-aligned (Béné, 2022). Furthermore, for a sustainability transformation, the exertion (or not) of agency of a diversity of food system actors needs to be examined (van Bers et al., 2019). Participatory, inclusive, and multi-actor governance models are a condition for ecological and social justice within food systems (Hammelman et al., 2020; Fesenfeld et al., 2023). Herein, as also emphasized by the UN New Urban Agenda, the role of cities in driving policy and action for sustainability via inclusive governance and growth is especially important (Sonnino & Coulson, 2021).

Expected outcomes and potential conflicts

Here, while some authors stress the potential of new governance models for sustainability, others are more critical. For example, Brons et al. (2022) state that urban living labs can engage citizens in co-creating healthy, inclusive, and sustainable food systems; Carrad et al. (2022) that dedicated food policies can strengthen the local food system and improve social and environmental outcomes; Zollet & Maharjan (2021) that democratic and participatory processes are important strategies for fostering sustainability a territorial level. On the other side, Horton (2024) warns that “not all food utopian narratives are necessarily aligned with principles of care, justice, and sustainability”, and Patay et al. (2023) that tensions between the three sustainability dimensions can impede the adoption of shared food system agendas. Furthermore, Sonnino (2023) and Thow et al. (2022) estimate that the implementation of holistic sustainability agendas is still difficult because of a current lack of integrated policies across sectors and siloed governance; and Wilkes (2022) that local and global policies are not substitutes, but complementary and interconnected. Overall, there seems to be consensus about reaching food system sustainability. However answering the how question remains challenging, i.e. which governance models, principles and strategies are most adequate to conciliate the three sustainability dimensions.

Result 3 - Current barriers in food system governance for sustainability and proposed solutions

Current barriers

Current barriers to food system governance for sustainability reported in the literature concerned different areas: research, policies, corporations, and governance models (Figure 2 below).

Concerning research, the following insufficiencies have been raised: a general underrepresentation of the governance topic within the food system domain (van Bers et al., 2019), a lack of empirical backing within the debates on food system transformation (Sonnino, 2023), a focus on food system outcomes rather than on the causes of unsustainability (Moragues-Faus et al., 2017), a gap of knowledge of multi-scale or networked governance forms (Delaney et al., 2018), an absence of metrics for sustainable food system governance (Landert et al., 2017), research too much focused on urban contexts (Zollet & Maharjan, 2021), little evidence of actual contributions of food policy councils to sustainability transitions (Michel et al., 2022), and underrepresentation of early career researchers (Russell et al., 2022). Moreover, Arthur et al. point out that “No single conceptualization or theorization is enough to fully address the constantly evolving social, economic, and environmental challenges that emerge from the food system.” [23]. Still, they recognize the prominent amount of literature produced in the past years on this topic.

Policy problems are also often mentioned in the literature, especially regarding: a non-linkage of especially international and global policies to on-the-ground realities (Mangnus et al., 2019; Ballamingie et al., 2020), an unbalanced policy engagement of local governments (Carrad et al., 2022), or processes being too bureaucratic, regardless of the scale (Carrad et al., 2023; Conneely & Mahon, 2015). Next, policies can be inconsistent or fragmented (del Valle et al., 2022), treating symptoms rather than structural causes (Hammelman et al., 2020), or imposed, top-down policies by governments (Levkoe et al., 2023). Among the critical issues, there are difficult translations of supra-national to national policies (Patay et al., 2023), tendencies to simplify complex socio-ecological processes to indicators or mere data (Sonnino & Coulson, 2021), or siloed governance resulting in limited coordination across issues and between sectors (Thow et al., 2022). Hence, although policy problems occur at different geographical scales, they are more likely associated with larger top-down, international, or national levels.

Some authors consider that large corporations are responsible for unequal and exclusive governance, especially due to a concentration of economic and market power (Russell et al., 2022; Béné, 2022; Clapp, 2021).

Other authors criticize current governance models as being determined by economic value and international trade (Eakin et al., 2017), inadequately responding to sustainability ambitions (Herens et al., 2022), determined by short-term transformation costs (Fesenfeld et al., 2023), and following the dominant neo-liberal, market-based systems (Pittore & Debons, 2023).

Proposed solutions

Solutions for science and policy, and proposed governance models and principles are multiple.

From science, it is recommended to act independently to inform policy decisions (Clapp, 2021). From the policy side, requirements concern: more coherence by better connecting different public institutions and articulations across scales (del Valle et al., 2022; Ballamingie et al., 2020), strong institutions, also at the global level (Johnson et al., 2023), and good governance principles in public policy as a precondition for achieving transformations (Wilkes, 2022).

Regarding innovations in governance, the most prominent types of organizations are Food Policy Councils (FPCs), Multiple-Stakeholder Platforms (MSPs), and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). FPCs are considered participatory, collaborative, and democratic approaches (Nadeau & Koebele, 2023; Fesenfeld et al., 2023), as experiments for shaping new governance models based on food justice values (Davey & Davis, 2022); and as being able to respond to food crises (Hammelman et al., 2020) or to scale up good practices ('seeds') (Mangnus et al., 2019). MSPs can bring together multi-sector actors into shared spaces for joint decision-making [39] (Pittore & Debons, 2023) and shape new governance models responding to sustainability goals if supported in developing stronger capabilities (Herens et al., 2022). CSOs are seen as being able to influence policy outcomes, contribute to more inclusive and democratic governance (Carrad et al., 2022), link policy and people, include communities and vulnerable people, and foster collaborations across sectors (Levkoe et al., 2023).

For enhancing governance principles, multi-actor collaboration and inclusion are considered crucial. More precisely, Arthur et al. (2022) and Sonnino (2023) propose multi-stakeholder collaboration across scales, disciplines, and sectors, Moragues-Faus et al. (2017) and Carrad et al. (2023) more democratic and integrated governance with shared responsibilities between diverse stakeholders and minimizing power differences. Moreover, several authors (Conneely & Mahon, 2015; Béné, 2022; Clapp, 2021) advocate for the re-empowerment of smaller agrifood system actors and civil society, and Davey & Davis (2022) even to rethink how "more radical food justice values". In general, reorganizing or prioritizing the common principles and values is recommended (del Valle et al., 2022; Wilkes, 2022; Brons et al., 2022; Eakin et al., 2017).

Figure 2: Current barriers in food system governance for sustainability and proposed solutions (own illustration; for the numbering please consult the **Source**: Donner, Mamès, de Vries (2024; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>)

5.1.4. Implications for new sustainable governance models

For achieving a transition to sustainability in food systems, governance models are to be reconsidered. These models should better articulate top-down and bottom-up approaches and be inclusive, for balancing the distribution of power and the value created. Hence, there should be more consideration from the policy side on how co-governance can be developed (Ballamingie et al., 2020). Governments are asked to create 'dedicated spaces' that enable discussing problems of market concentration and power distribution in food systems (Clapp, 2021). In these discussions, the private food sector should not be excluded, because it is part of the solution as the largest employing sector in Europe. Furthermore, food systems should be based on multi-layered governance structures involving local organizations with more expertise, as in the case of Protected Geographical Indications (Conneely & Mahon, 2015), and move beyond singular topics as food is not only a material issue but includes other elements of life such as environment, health and well-being (Levkoe et al., 2023). This is also underlined by Jackson et al. (2021), who consider food as a commodity, human right, or common good.

New governance models should also encompass multiple geographical scales and administrative boundaries (Hammelman et al., 2020). This would help improve local-regional and regional–national as well as international dialogues and provide better solutions for funding and capacity development (Patay et al., 2023). Food system governance should avoid being siloed and be coupled with other sector policies; sustainability certification for example should be part of a policy mix supporting not just a single commodity but farming systems as a whole (Thompson et al., 2022).

Finally, it is recommended that governance models are adaptive and coherent. In the case of the EU, Fesenfeld et al. (2023) stress the need to develop a common definition of a sustainable European food system and a concrete food systems governance structure based on principles of adaptability and connectivity. In section 5.1 and chapter 6, a new conceptual framework and definition is therefore discussed.

5.2. Empirical study of governance architectures of existing Partnerships and 'large joint initiatives' (see annex 1 and 2)

5.2.1. Empirical Study of governance architectures of partnerships

The empirical study of governance architectures has revealed an interesting series of governance models for a range of running or starting partnerships, and other large comparable initiatives (see Annex 1). These are the following ones (for further reading, please consult references at the end of this section):

- EU Partnership: BIODIVERSITY (BIODIVERSA+)
- EU Partnership: BLUE ECONOMY
- EU Partnership: ASSESSMENT OF RISK FROM CHEMICALS (PARC)

- EU Partnership Water4ALL
- PRIMA Mediterranean Partnership
- BBI Biobased Industry Consortium (today CBE-JU)
- EIT FOOD (EIT, 2024)
- Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) Healthy Diets for Healthy Living (HDHL)
- Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (FACCE)
- ERANET SUSFOOD2 (SUSFOOD, 2020)
- EJP RARE DISEASES (EJP, 2021)
- GLOBAL GOVERNANCE OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE (AMR, 2024)

The examples illustrate the importance of several building blocks in the governance architecture of Partnerships, namely: (i) Governance Board and/or Executive Committee, (ii) Operational management committee (including a secretariat), (iii) Task forces (related to work packages and daily partnership activities), (iv) Advisory Board including science and stakeholder advice, (v) European, national and sub-national coordination levels in interaction with each other, and (vi) bottom-up approaches in food system labs, platforms, etc. Previously, quite some of these elements have already been taken into account in the governance chapter of the narrative of the Partnership on SFS.

Disclaimer: the here presented architectures may be changed in time due to the further developments of each partnership.

5.2.2. Preparatory work on governance in the narrative, template, and SRIA P-SFS

Also, the preparatory work on governance architectures from the Narrative, Template, and SRIA of the Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems is included in this Deliverable (ANNEX 2).

In the Narrative, two separate governance architectures have been proposed that were united in the following Figure 3.

Figure 3. Possible governance structure of the partnership (retrieved from the Narrative P-SFS).

This schematic representation has not been changed in the succeeding Template and SRIA of the Partnership on SFS. It includes:

- **Governing board (GB):** the highest-level decision-making body. Will be formed by partners representing program owners across Europe and from the European Commission. It should also ensure that both macro and place-based priorities are considered.
- **Management board (MB):** will support the GB and is responsible for day-to-day management, initiating and overseeing the Partnerships' activities. Will include the coordinator, co-coordinator, and hub leaders.
- **EU Food systems Executive Office (FSEO):** will implement the defined actions according to the established work plans, performing the R&I activities and establishing an interface between science and policy. FSEO will be constituted by the Hub leaders, Task leaders, and Partners.
- **EU Food Systems Hub of Hubs (FSHH):** will consider the National hubs (NH) and Thematic hubs (TH), which will closely interact with the Collaboration Partners Platform (CPP).
 - **National hubs (NH):** national networking bodies regarding the thematic of the partnership, gathering the national expertise on these subjects and federating/framing relevant initiatives at local and regional levels.
 - **Thematic hubs (TH):** transnational hubs dedicated to specific subjects/common themes under the umbrella of the partnership, corresponding to "system thinking hubs".
- **Collaboration Partners Platform (CPP)/Ambassadors:** should include the representatives of the different actors playing a role in the definition and implementation of safe and sustainable food systems. CPP will consider the Food Systems Community of Practice, Private Partners, and representatives of diverse civil society and other stakeholder groups. A youth group or youth ambassador system should be part of it.
- **Advisory board (AB):** provide advice to the MB on the planning and implementation of the main activities of the partnership.

The different bodies will target some key specificities of the Partnership like the Knowledge Hub of FS Labs, and different actor groups (relevant in inclusive partnerships).

Also, the narrative detailed an argumentation for developing a **co-funded partnership**, underlining the need to align European funding with national funding. This allows for substantially increasing budgets for synergistic topics in Europe.

However, the Narrative also stressed the need for aligning public and private goals, jointly. This would suggest a need for an (additional) **co-programmed partnership, or even an institutionalized partnership**. In such a partnership, all kinds of actors are directly involved in all activities and their governance. Such a partnership seems to correspond most closely to an **inclusive Partnership** at all levels of its structure and functioning.

Finally, the narrative provided suggestions for categories of **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** like (i) commitment of stakeholders, (ii) contributions to activities, (iii) relevant focus areas, (iv) alignment of activities, (v) mutual benefits, (vi) performance of Partnership activities and (vii) attractiveness of the Partnership to inspire others.

In the elaboration of the Template, the schematic representation has also been used, but other additional elements have not been given. The following comment has been added: *'It should be noted that further elaboration of the Governance structure in the template would include a reflection on a most suitable governance structure for a mission-driven approach to the Partnership, which may ensure that over time the portfolio of projects funded through competitive calls will cover as much of the SRIA and Roadmap as possible and that results (outputs) from individual projects feed into the necessary outcomes in terms of Safe and sustainable food systems following an explicit impact pathway. This means the R&I solutions aim to respond to the grand food system challenges in a holistic and systemic manner: economy, environment, and societal solutions require horizontal collaboration. It should include reflections on a potential role for*

the SCAR Food Systems Strategic Working Group, which is the convening platform for co-creating the Partnership. Moreover, a comparison of different governance models is then recommended'.

In the SRIA, new elements were added, however, a new visual representation had not been given. Distinguishable stakeholder groups were identified:

- (i) The **'Partners of the P-SFS Consortium'**, essentially consist of partners from ministries and funding agencies, however all others who will sign the P-SFS-Grant with the EC, like regions, associated partners, private sector actors, etc.
- (ii) **The 'Applicants of P-SFS Funding'**, are the actors that apply for grants delivered via open calls by the P-SFS Consortium.
- (iii) **The 'Potential future Partnership SFS Consortium'**, grouping actors that are jointly willing to guarantee the continuation of the Partnership during and **after** the 7-year grant provided by the EC.
- (iv) **The 'wider public'** are actors that are benefiting from the sustainability impact created by the Partnership and provide feedback to the Partners or Applicants in one way or the other.

In addition, international cooperation is foreseen with Europe's priority partner countries and regions on the manifold cross-border dimensions of Europe's food systems. Finally, the notion that the transition to SFS only may be achieved together with the seven other Partnerships in Cluster 6 of HE, requires regular exchanges and a well-founded cooperation scheme.

In the SRIA, also The thematic Area 4 **'Change the way we govern'** (from the SRIA, and a thematic area in FutureFoodS) is described. Its subtitle is: *Leverage points for local, national, EU, and global transition pathways, and co-creation, including private ones like the Farm-to-Fork code of conduct & local initiatives (e.g. cities)*. This thematic area targets research and innovation needs in the governance of food systems. It doesn't target the governance of partnerships itself, however, it **may provide new insights that will become relevant for the governance of the partnership itself**. Examples are the understanding and new knowledge on roles and power balances of different actors (targeting inclusivity), and governance challenges over different scales (and different actors involved).

Since the full text of this Thematic Area 4 is relevant for governance model considerations of the Partnership, the integral text is included in ANNEX 2.

5.2.3. Other inspiring governance model suggestions

- i. The first inspiring and highly complete set of suggestions for governance models relevant to Partnerships is provided by the European Commission itself. In particular, this concerns the Model Consortium Agreement for ERA-NET-Cofund actions (please see for full document: <https://www.era-learn.eu/support-for-partnerships/governance-administration-legal-base/governance-structure-and-committees>). It is based on the DESCA Horizon 2020 Model. Section 6 targets the Governance structure.
- ii. The second inspiring example stems also from the EC, namely from the 3S strategies of regions (Pontikakis et al. 2022; page 46, Figure 4). In particular, the multi-level elements are included that are highly relevant for a European Partnership, as well as both funding and knowledge building up are integrated (Pontikakis et al., 2022).

Figure 4. A multi-level partnership tackling challenges (retrieved from Pontikakis et al., 2022)

- iii. The third inspiring governance model originates from literature and reflects on system approaches in governance (see Figure 5; Katina et al., 2019). This model is especially relevant for the new Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems because all topics in the Partnership are considered from a Food System Lens. The intention will be to place food system approaches at the core of the Partnership, however, a sound conceptual approach is lacking. The following figure provides therefore insightful considerations.

Figure 5. Complex system governance (CSG)'s metasystem system functions (retrieved from Polinpapilinho et al. 2019 and slightly modified)

If food systems approaches, and generally systemic ways of working, are at the heart of ideal European partnerships, then their operational processes may be schematically presented as in Figure 6.

Figure 6. A simplified, transparent, operational process for food system approaches in an ideal partnership; RIPE = Research, innovation, policy, and education (own design).

5.2.4. Synthesis

The large variety of governance architectures and our interpretation of these, preparatory work in the narrative of the P-SFS, and inspiring examples reveal that a European Ideal Partnership has quite some flexibility in structuring its governance. Still, several key elements emerge:

- Scales, scaling, and scale interactions are crucially important in Partnerships operating from local to EU levels (and beyond).
- The dynamics in governing partnerships should get particular attention because the P-SFS is dealing with systemic approaches in entire food systems; within the governance architecture different organs should then also be well connected to permit fluxes of knowledge, services, financial means, regulations, etc.
- Inclusivity asks for not only involvement in the advisory board but also active roles in all tasks of a partnership; this requires clear and responsible roles in the different governance organs.
- The ideal partnership concerns both funding (external calls) and internal activities to accelerate the transition towards sustainable food systems. This requires task forces with separate roles and also ‘fire walls’ to avoid conflicts of interest. However, exchanges between them are primordial to realize sustainability goals.

As a first attempt, above elements are generalized in the following governance architecture (Figure 7).

Figure 7. ‘ A generic schematic representation of governance architecture for Partnerships in Europe (partly inspired by value network maps of Dentoni et al., 2022; own design)

This scheme is just a first version of a generic governance architecture, and connections between the different organs. It still needs to be discussed with different stakeholder groups and partnerships. Hence, it is work in progress. It also needs to be combined with a framework that defines the regulations, roles, and responsibilities, bottom-up driving forces, and top-down orchestration processes to reach partnership objectives and to balance inputs of all actors (see chapter 6).

In the last year of FOODPathS, these elements will be further discussed and become part of the Deliverable ‘Manual of the partnership version 2.0’.

5.3. Findings on governance from mirror group perspectives

As part of the process of understanding the key components of an innovative governance model for a sustainable food systems partnership, questions and early findings were shared with ‘mirror group’ participants for review, reflection, and input. They were also included in ‘mirroring activities’ at workshops and events (<https://www.foodpaths.eu/in-action/partnership-inclusivity/>). FoodPathS ‘mirror groups’ bring together organizations and initiatives that are not directly involved in the project, but may be impacted by it and/or have valuable related experience to contribute. These *mirror group* participants learn about and reflect on the work happening in the project/partnership to provide useful input and recommendations to ensure that activities and decision making are as inclusive and impactful as possible. FoodPathS partners organised three mirror groups, 1) with individuals and organisations based in Europe, 2) a second with organisations and individuals based outside of Europe, and 3) a third with organisations and individuals based in either Europe or outside of Europe (some who previously attended a mirror group and some who had not).

Additionally, as part of ‘mirroring activities,’ questions about critical elements and lessons learned related to establishing an inclusive governance model for a sustainable food system were asked and reflected upon in workshops and events organised by FoodPathS partners within Europe and beyond – Finland, Denmark, Italy, Brasil, Vietnam to name a few. These mirror group meetings and mirroring activities provide critical input, grounded in the experience of sustainable food systems professionals, into the development of an ideal governance model for the future partnership for sustainable food system transformation. The results provide important ‘lived experience’ context to the literature review and case studies.

In order to make food system governance inclusive, transparent, and adaptive, reducing trade-offs and fostering co-benefits across diverse contexts (FOODPathS Deliverable D7.1), participants reflected on the information and questions FoodPathS provided – based on literature reviews, case studies, and the analysis of FoodPathS partners. Participants shared from their own experiences that partnerships that are overly ‘top-down,’ hierarchical and obtuse in their administration and decision making processes result in activities that benefit ‘few’ rather than ‘many,’ and create spaces that are exclusive to individuals and organisations that are already engaged in the EU level sphere of food systems work. However, in order to truly transform food systems, the input, experience, and needs of a broad range of actors is needed.

Five key themes for recommendations emerged from the mirroring groups and activities, to date – knowledge exchange, moving beyond traditional donor-partner dynamics, balancing bias and power, context specific communication, and establishing clear, transparent, and tailored decision making and administrative systems. Effective knowledge exchange is essential for fostering inclusive, impactful, and sustainable collaboration in today’s interconnected, global, world. This requires a deliberate effort to include diverse stakeholders, particularly those with direct connection to people ‘working on the ground’ in food systems and those from or representing marginalized or informal sectors, in decision-making processes. Moving beyond traditional donor-partner dynamics, a shift toward equitable co-creation and shared learning is crucial for building trust and achieving meaningful, long-term impact from any investment of private or tax-payer funds. Ensuring a balanced representation of voices and creating bias-free environments can further promote inclusivity, while tailored communication and transparent processes help make participation accessible to all, regardless of cultural or institutional contexts; balanced does not always mean equal. It could be that there are some entities not included in some decision making or that some inputs are limited to particular topics. Setting up processes that respect that

engagement by different actors will differ is critical. Key values underpinning these five principles are: adaptable, transparent, and equitable. By embedding these principles and themes, partnerships can establish frameworks that support genuine collaboration and innovation across political, sectoral, and geographic boundaries.

Key recommendations:

Strengthen knowledge exchange

Promote knowledge exchange by ensuring all stakeholders, including marginalized and informal sector actors, are represented and actively participate in decision making processes. Create environments where all voices are valued and heard.

Move beyond traditional donor-partner dynamics.

Shift the focus from efficiency-driven models to fostering meaningful impact and continuous learning. Partnerships should emphasize co-creation, shared learning, equitable collaboration to build trust, long-term sustainability, and the establishment of spaces 'to do something differently.'

Balance voices and avoid bias

Establish a culture of co-creation and collaboration. Create 'safer' spaces to prevent power imbalances and bias in decision-making processes. Ensure smaller and marginalized groups, and networks representing them, are given platforms to voice their concerns and proposals

Tailor communication to specific contexts

Understand and adapt to the specific cultural and operational contexts of stakeholders. This includes simplifying technical language, reducing bureaucratic barriers, and ensuring terminology is accessible to all, particularly those not already deeply engaged in EU-level activities.

Establish clear and transparent processes, points of contact, and support structures

Establish clear pathways for input, and designated points of contact for organisations and individuals in each Member State and for entities outside of the EU. Non-European countries, in particular, may need to receive additional technical support to navigate governance structures and ensure equitable access to resources.

5.4. Governance ‘in-vivo’ insights from case studies

As shown in this Deliverable report, governance in multi-stakeholder initiatives can take various forms depending on a wide range of factors, including the kind of actors involved and the degree of cooperation between partners. Going deeper into the characterization of governance models in multi-stakeholder initiatives within food systems, two different studies have been carried out. One concerns an overview of 52 multi-stakeholder initiatives in food systems selected by partners of the WPs 4&7 and described in Deliverable 2.1. The other one is an in-depth study of 4 partnerships by interviewing 10 different partners for each case, including field visits. Overall findings have been reported in Deliverable 2.3. These studies have been further analyzed by the INRAE team through the angle of governance; this is here described. For all details on the methodologies employed for these two studies, please consult deliverables D2.1 and D2.3.

5.4.1. An overview of 52 cases to learn from the diversity of governance models

The collection of 52 multi-stakeholder food systems partnerships – that were collected and described by the partners of the WPs 4&7 using a single template based on the structure of a game (see ANNEX 3; de Vries et al., 2022 and 2024) – reflects a wide diversity of backgrounds, contexts, structures, activities, and visions. From industrial clusters to civil-society-driven projects, these examples provide a wealth of information on governance models of multi-stakeholder initiatives within food systems. At the governance workshop on ‘Governance and Scenarios’ during the annual meeting in Rome, on the 27th of June 2023, a first definition of governance of food systems was used from literature: governance concerns the “processes and actors constellations that shape decision-making and activities ultimately aiming at the realization of food availability, food access, and food utilization, and their stability over time” (Delaney et al., 2018; van Bers et al., 2019); please see Section 5.1 for more details. Based on the literature review, we have provided our definition ‘the continuous process of orchestration of policies and (multiple) food systems consisting of diverse interacting actors, respecting (in)formal rules and striving to provide food for all, in equitable and environmentally-friendly ways, at any time and in any context’ and an innovative governance model (Donner, Mamès, de Vries., 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>; [Figure in chapter 6](#)).

The latter definition is directly related to the game structure-based template. Within this template, five elements can be related to our governance definition: food actors, boundary conditions, actor’s strength, flexibility of actors, and interactions between diverse actors. Information gathered for each element has been categorized and presented in the form of graphs below.

5.4.2. Results and analysis of governance elements from case studies

Each histogram in this section shows the number of cases – out of the 52 cases studied – on the vertical axis (ordinate axis) per element with distinguished categories on the horizontal axis (abscissa axis).

Food actors

In the first histogram, most cases (about 40 of the 52 analyzed) include research and private companies, hence underlining their innovation focus. Public institutions (32 cases) and producers (22 cases) follow them. NGOs and civil society organizations are underrepresented in many cases. This may be due to innovation as a dominant orientation in cases, in which they are not directly involved. A lack of e.g. technological knowledge could be a barrier. Inclusivity – one significant criterion of sustainable governance – is thus not visible in all cases; hence, this requires attention soon. For instance, in projects leading to radical changes in a specific area, it may be important to consider the involvement of local people's and NGOs' opinions, for example in Living Lab projects. Governance is impacted by the kind of actors involved in the partnership. Including more categories of actors could be challenging to manage but also more democratic.

Boundary conditions

Boundary conditions provide a framework for the actions of the partnership. It could limit actions but also provide opportunities for innovations. Legislation is the first boundary condition identified in many cases (19 of the 52), and the second is 'market conditions' (16 cases). It typically concerns conditions with which actors cannot interfere directly. These are imposed and often only marginally influenced by the partnership's action. They can form either a serious threat and unfavorable context or a chance and level playing field since every actor is subject to the same rules. This may lead to increasing performance and possible innovations. Third, a contract (13 cases) directly defines the framework of a partnership. It could be at some time a burden or an opportunity depending on the operating flexibility it provides. If quality requirements (11 cases) are the basis of partnership acts, they may represent opportunities for creativity. Private and government support is also identified as important (about 12 cases each) since it provides funds that are essential for the initiative. It is interesting to remark that this is not the first identified boundary condition even though it is generally considered as a *sine qua non* condition for an initiative to start and run. Quite some cases have other sources of funding. Languages could also be a barrier, especially in the case of cross-country initiatives and regarding international communication on partnership actions.

Actors' strength

Regarding the actor's strength, expertise appears as the most important pillar (37 cases). Knowledge of partners is thus at the core of the studied partnerships. Second is their search for synergies (17 cases). This in combination with the high level of expertise (knowledge) could have a significant impact. Third, leadership and clear vision are put forward (both 5 cases), hence allowing to creation of impact at high levels. Finally, materials (9 cases) are mentioned as assets that can be shared, providing means to create links between partners and strengthen partnerships.

Actors' flexibility

Actor's flexibility is the ability of each actor to adapt to the partnership's needs while taking into account its interests. 'Openness of mind' is the first factor shared in many cases (22 cases out of 52). If openness of mind is an important condition for partners to join a multi-stakeholder partnership, it is not always

visible or even put into practice as the cases reveal. This element is followed by the 'willingness to share' (14 cases), which goes beyond openness of mind in terms of cooperation. Technical adaptation (9 cases) remains very specific to partnership goals and involves a high degree of engagement and trust from partners. For some cases (7 cases) the flexibility of the pre-defined roadmap has been underlined: it is stated to be an important element for the resilience of a partnership. On the contrary, market trend dependency is considered a non-flexibility factor; it compels actors to make certain choices.

Interactions between actors

This section first requires better defining² the classification of a 'wide range of possible interaction forms'. Some key different concepts are here classified from the strongest form of 'working together' to the weakest, using definitions from the Cambridge Dictionary (2024; <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/>):

- **Partnership:** an agreement between organizations, people, etc. to work together
- **Cluster:** a group of similar things or people to form a group, sometimes surrounding something or someone, or to make something do this
- **Alliance:** a group of countries, political parties, or people who have agreed to work together because of shared interests or aims.
- **Network:** people that you know, considered as a group whose members exchange information with each other.
- **Cooperation:** the act of working together with someone or doing what they ask you.
- **Interactions:** an occasion when two or more people or things communicate with or react to each other.

Partnership, cluster, alliance, and network embody the idea of structured groups working together toward a common goal for a certain time. In contrast, cooperation and interactions convey the idea of punctual collaboration that could be repeated through time (own statement). It is interesting to notice that only 5 cases are partnerships as defined above. 23 cases are described as clusters. These seem to be the most common form of 'interactions' together with 'cooperation' (16 cases). One important remark is that 'cluster' is a word especially used in the private sector and seems to have an interpretation nearly similar to the one of partnership. It is well-known by industrial actors because of M. Porter's cluster theory (<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=2cbe5b01c61edee8dc7cd97fdeb8b7bf9ed3a117>) and its definition as 'geographically close actors working together to achieve a

² All the definitions are provided by Cambridge online dictionary <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/>

competitive advantage'. Many cases concern simple interactions punctually (8 cases). A minority of initiatives could be considered as network (5 cases) or alliance (4 cases). Overall, strong forms of interactions (and collaboration) are more represented (35 cases in total) than the weakest forms (15 cases in total).

5.4.3. Discussion: lessons learned from the cases - recommendations

Results are presented as forms of observations, by crossing insights from the previous section.

Observation 1: A discrete place of funders in governance models

The analysis of results reveals that funders are not present in a majority of the cases studied. This could be considered surprising due to their importance in supporting a (new) collective initiative. However, alternatively, it may be considered logical because of avoiding 'conflicts of interest' and keeping strict barriers between funders and beneficiaries. It is also not excluded that in some cases funders are not explicitly mentioned but are implicitly involved in the private and public actor groups as a kind of co-funders of the 'initiative'. Still, it is worth underlining that most of the studied collective initiatives are running without the direct visible involvement of funders. For example, some of the initiatives require annual fees from partners to run the initiative, hence external funding may not be needed. Other initiatives are fully publicly-funded, and funders do not play a central role in governance and strategy design. This may be because different stakeholders involved can provide all required knowledge on topics of concern. Still, one notices also that new elements are provided due to the gained expertise of funders in past decades like national, regional, or local funding agencies as well as philanthropic organizations like Cariplo, Daniel and Nina Carasso, Agropolis, and other Foundations. This may help in innovating the wide range of partnerships of the future.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

This observation is particularly important since it converges with the results of the "society survey" about an ideal partnership carried out by FOODPathS partners over the summer of 2024 (Deliverable D8.3 'Feedback from society'). To the question "What kind of stakeholder should have a prominent role in the Partnership SFS?", only 7% of the respondents listed public and private investors, while Research organizations & universities received 24% and government institutions 18% of scores. One interpretation can be that stakeholders want to prioritize the voices of actors who are directly involved in the partnership. Another interpretation can be that funders are hidden (i.e. 'not explicitly mentioned') in public and private actor categories. A third interpretation is that 'own or co-funding' is often not transparently appearing in Partnerships. The 'own' contribution of each involved actor in a Partnership can be substantial e.g. in terms of provided in-kind person months, materials and services, infrastructure, etc. In R&I projects, this is often well specified, and also for the institutionalized partnerships like Circular-BioBased Europe, but less apparent in other partnerships. **Thus, it may be important to re-discuss the place and role of funders (and funding actors) in a partnership and their equal (or not) footing with other actors. Besides, the study on 52 cases proved that other governance models are also highly worthwhile to consider for future European Partnerships.**

Observation 2: Actors' strengths, especially their expertise, and flexibility, should be best valorised

Expertise appears to be the main strength of partners in a Partnership; it should be made visible and valorized as such to help create synergies with each other in a Partnership. To that extent, the actor's flexibility is framing the potential of constructive exchanges between partners. 'Openness of mind' and 'willingness to share' can enhance knowledge transfer. For many reasons (i.e. competition, rivalry, plagiarism, cultural gaps, and language gaps (including in technical languages) ...), some partners are afraid of knowledge transfer and sharing their expertise. At some points, it could be a real burden for the partnership if leverages are not found and trust between partners is insufficient.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

This reflection reminds us how precious knowledge owned by the partners is, and how important it is to capitalize on knowledge before transferring it to others and discovering potentially new applications. Partnerships are one of the places where expertise is exchanged and discussed. This implies a high responsibility from the partnership to be creative in collecting and valorizing inputs in a transparent and trustful manner. The flexibility of all actors regarding expertise input should be openly discussed. If this is not well-understood and respected before starting a partnership, it negatively impacts mind-openness and willingness to share. Our case studies reveal that their partnership initiatives are running well since both openness of mind and willingness to share score high. Other tools such as confidentiality agreements and meetings in small groups can further help to lower barriers to knowledge and expertise exchange. **It is up to the partnership to listen to each partner and frame context-adapted tools to foster dialogue. Flexibility depends on the creation of an atmosphere of trust, an important factor allowing to best mobilize the actors' strengths. To get a robust and resilient partnership, it thus recommended to respect the time necessary to listen to each partner, understand their (complementary) expertise and knowledge, build trust, train people in new forms of collaboration and collective intelligence, and avoid placing competition within the core of the Partnership.**

Observation 3: Lack of clarity on the vocabulary of collaborative initiatives, relative to the partnership concept

Concerning the interactions between actors within the initiatives, a classification with precise definitions of some key terms has been made in the previous section. Regarding the huge variety of terms (partnership, alliance, network, cluster, cooperation, interaction...) and the subtlety of the differences between them, some concepts could be seen as vague and are not correctly used.

→ **Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships**

The feedback from the 2024 FOODPathS survey (Deliverable D8.3) to the question “what kind of stakeholder should have a prominent role in the Partnership SFS?” illustrates some confusion and misunderstanding. Some respondents misunderstood that the focus of the survey was on the Partnership as defined by the European Commission (Co-funded, co-programmed, etc.). They also considered partner consortia in R&I projects as partnerships. Despite the definition provided by the EC, the partnership concept is still quite nebulous for many actors. **It is thus a real necessity to better communicate and explain the partnership definition.** A good governance model should put internal and external communication at its core if a diversity of actors is involved, taking into account its statute as a partnership. **Thus, it is recommended that partnerships take time to define what they are, how and where they operate, why they act, as well as how they situate themselves compared to other partnership concepts. This should be clear for every partner and also be communicated by each partner similarly.**

5.4.4. An in-depth case study to learn about operating governance forms

After having collected many examples of food system cases (D2.1), thanks to the support of the WP4 and WP7 partners, in-depth case studies were conducted on 4 ‘partnerships’. These reflect the diversity of scales and cover countries in the north, south, east, and west of Europe:

- Neighborhood Hubs Against Food Waste (urban, city of Milan),
- Pôle Mer Méditerranée (regional, France),
- Foodwest (regional/national, Finland) and
- BIOEAST (cross-countries, Central-Eastern countries of European Union).

These cases have been analyzed from various angles: co-creation, intermediaries, and governance. Overall results about governance have been reported in D2.3 and hence are here only included in the ANNEX as reference material (ANNEX 4). A snapshot of the interview guide on the governance part can be found in ANNEX 5. Here, two schematic presentations of the four in-depth cases as well as major observations are presented (Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8. Four cases briefly presented

Figure 9. Some key findings per in-depth case study; more details in Annex 4 and D2.3

5.5. Scenarios of possible governance models (workshop Rome, June 2023)

In June 2023, a dedicated workshop on ‘inclusive governance and scenarios’ was held in Rome³. The duration of the workshop was 90 minutes. All partners of FOODPathS were represented to give their input and views on governance.

Rationale of the workshop: As stated in the Call text for FOODPathS, inclusiveness is crucial for the future Partnership, both in its consortium constitution as well as in its governance. Then, a wide variety of actors, with different ways of operating and governing are involved. A major question emerges: ‘How to develop a governance model that incorporates inclusiveness and respects scales of operations of actors (from local to global)?’ Also, the ‘rate’ of governance, from completely self-organized-without-steering to strongly top-down-governed operations is a relevant point of attention.

Aim of the workshop: to discuss and clarify what it means to build an inclusive governance model for future partnerships. This was translated into the following objectives:

- provide elements on the concepts of “governance” and “governance in the food systems”;
- report on experiences within and outside FoodPaths on inclusive governance models; and
- engage participants in discussions about their vision of possible governance models for the future partnership.

Ambitions of the workshop:

- to reach an increased awareness about inclusive and participatory governance models for transitions in food systems
- to develop shared visions about what inclusive governance could look like for the partnership.

5.5.1. The agenda of the workshop:

1. A short introduction about research findings on inclusive and participatory governance:
 - ❖ What is governance?
 - In theory
 - In food systems
 - How is it operationalized?
 - ❖ What are existing models of governance that are participatory and democratic:
 - In multi-stakeholder platforms for driving change in food systems for sustainability – like policy councils
 - In multi-stakeholder initiatives for innovation towards sustainability in food systems – like living labs and observatories
 - Key success factors are related to scales and inter-scalar relations, e.g. how can smaller scale initiatives interact with higher scale ones?
2. With all representatives of FoodPathS partners, a visioning and scenario-building exercise about potential governance models for the future partnership. The outline of this exercise is as follows: the participants were asked to
 - Formulate and discuss a core (shared) question;
 - Draw a chart with 2 axes, revealing extremes. An example is provided in the following Figure 10.

³Working with scenarios (based on previous methodologies developed by Shell, Wageningen, INRAE and others) has also been elaborated in the SCAR strategic working group on food systems: <https://scar-europe.org/food-deliverables>

Figure 10. A chart to build four contrasting scenarios.

- Identify and characterize 4 scenarios (visions of potential futures)*. Give hereby elements for visualizing the 4 different scenarios like drawings, film titles, specific features, etc. The facilitator will put these elements together to make a unified scenario;
- Challenge the scenarios to define some key features for each scenario;
- Translate each scenario into a governance model, and discuss for each model its 'inclusiveness';
- Identify how your initiatives as a partner fit or not (hence, are conflicting) with each scenario (an example is provided in the figure 11 below).

Initiatives	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	
Urban Food Policy	+++	0	--	+	
National technological platform	0	+++	++	--	Strong Fit Neutral Strong Conflict
Observatory	0	---	--	+	+++ 0 ---
....					++ --
					+ -

Figure 11. Prioritizing initiatives with respect to four scenarios

*A further detailed explanation of scenarios was presented. Scenarios are (i) **Plausible** (Logical, consistent, and believable), (ii) **Relevant** (highlight key challenges and dynamics of the future), (iii) **Divergent** (differ from one another in strategically significant ways and (iv) **Challenging** (challenge fundamental beliefs and assumptions of people concerned).

Scenarios should:

- **Provoke thinking** rather than provide answers AND should help in **guiding** us.
- Be **contrasting** to face potential extreme futures and not be biased by only searching for positive options.

- Be **evidence-based** and thoroughly discussed by experts in the field.
Hence, scenarios do **not** present **real** futures, but elements of it.

3. End with a plenary discussion on the outcomes of the vision and key elements for inclusive governance models.

5.5.2. The results of the workshop

First, a short presentation introduced key conceptual elements and literature insights about what is meant by “governance” in the food system and how we can operationalize such concepts in our co-construction of an inclusive governance partnership. The presentation started with some definitions of “governance” and with some concrete examples of governance tools. These included both formal and state-led institutions and tools and private mechanisms and civil society initiatives (see figures 12 and 13 below).

Figure 12. Formal and state-led institutions and tools

Figure 13. Private Mechanisms and Civil Society Initiatives

Then, the presentation referred to different studies pointing out the need to build governance models capable of catalyzing collective action and cooperation of key players in the food system, for effective transitions towards sustainability. Some of these studies have been included in the review paper as presented in Section 5.1. The presentation outlined some key questions that we can ask about a governance model to understand if it enables inclusive governance:

- Who participates?
- How do they participate?
- What are the outcomes of the decision-making process and who benefits from the outcomes?

The presentation also discussed questions related to the scale and inter-scaling of governance mechanisms. This is highly relevant for the partners – and their networks – in FOODPathS because they operate from local to global scales and vice versa. Finally, it proposed an example of an application of such a study, on a multistakeholder partnership for waste and food aid management in Milan, Italy (this work is currently further elaborated; a first case description had been presented in Deliverable D2.1; see figure 14 below).

Figure 14. A Case study of a governance model analysis

In the second phase of the workshop participants were invited to engage in an exercise of scenario development of possible governance models of a future partnership. The methodology of the exercise was explained, drawing from training courses and experiences of the project coordinator at Shell, Wageningen UR, and INRAE. Also, a concrete example has been given that was used at the World Economic Forum to produce scenarios on the future of global food systems, in 2017.

The methodology proposed to the participants the following:

- Formulate a common question: **Which future governance models may exist for a future Partnership?**
- Draw the following 2 axes relevant to the core question:
 - *Local versus EU-wide /global;*
 - *Isolated versus connected (or individually vs collectively).*
- Imagine 4 different scenarios for future governance models that fit in the 2-dimensional plot, described with a short title, one or more images, and a very short description.
- Via ‘wind-tunneling’ and for all participants, consider which scenario(‘s) fit(s) best with each participant’s organization and activities.

The participants were then divided into two different groups, producing the following results.

Group 1

	L. Riders	Globally Connected Network	Food System Islands	Connected networks of FS Valleys
ERIAFF Network representative	--	+++	-	++
SVS Foods representative	0	+++	---	0
ICLEI representative	---	+++	+	++
INRAE representative	0	+++	0	++

Legend :

Strong(er)(est) fits	Neutral	Strong(er)(est) Conflicts
+++	0	-
++		--
+		---

Figure 15. The outcomes of the scenarios & governance workshop of group 1

Group 2

	competing local silos	competitive global islands	collective disconnection	sharing world
research funders HDHL representative	—	-	++	+++
BIOEAST representative	-	-	+	+
Philanthropic representative	—	-	+	+++
Cities representative	+	—	+++	+
One Planet Network representative	—	—	-	+++
Consumers representative	-	0	++	+

Legend: similar to group 1

Figure 16. The outcomes of the scenarios & governance workshop of group 2

Disclaimer: the scores for each partner are proposed by representatives of the organizations present at the workshop, however, do not reflect the scores provided by the Boards of the organizations. Hence, these results should only be considered as a first attempt to understand the methodology, its relevance for organizations to verify their potential positionings, and the positions of collaborating partners, in future scenarios.

6. Implications of work done and conceptualizing of an ideal governance model for the P-SFS

As elaborated in the systematic literature review paper, summarized in section 5.1, a new conceptual framework has been proposed for the governance of food systems striving to reach sustainability (Donner, Mamès, de Vries, 2024). This is presented in the core of the following Figure 17. Key elements retrieved from existing literature, combined with our analysis have resulted in a governance model based on four main elements:

- The interactions between a diversity of actors that defined a partnership, or any other cooperation form. These interactions may have different strengths corresponding to the intensity of exchanges between actors;
- The control and power balances in food system partnerships. From management literature (and our work), we have distinguished four different zones: (i) the control zone, which represents the core 'business' of an actor (public, private,..), (ii) the adaptation zone, mimicking the capability of an actor to adapt to changing conditions, (iii) the co-creation zone, that describes joint actions of multiple actors, and (iv) the environment zone, that defines the context for partnerships of multi-actors. The latter can only be partially influenced by the Partnership; it especially also includes the challenges that a Partnership faces like climate change. Remarkably, these four zones correspond with one of the basic scientific theories, namely the unification theory in physics. The unification theory tries to provide a frame for the strong, weak, electromagnetic, and gravitation forces (de Vries et al., 2022; Donner et al., 2024). These well resemble the four zones as schematically presented in the Figure.
- The (in)formal rules, norms, values, limits, and practices that set the scene for partnerships to operate. A parallel with the game structure used in Deliverable D2.1 can be made. These define the boundaries and playing fields within which games can be played.
- The orchestration of all activities to face challenges, jointly orchestrate actions, and reach sustainable outcomes. Due to the overwhelming challenges that food systems (and all systems) are facing, a new way of orchestration multiple food systems is proposed that is inclusive, fair, environmentally friendly, and economically viable. As arguments, this requires that the overall global food system respects planetary and social limits (Rockström et al., 2009; Ostrom, 2009; Raworth, 2017) and balances between upper and lower limits for each sustainability indicator; since, the global food system is an 'ensemble of food sub-systems this also holds for all interacting food systems (de Vries et al., 2021).

Figure 17. A novel conceptual framework for the governance of food systems striving to reach sustainable outcomes (retrieved from Donner et al., 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>; slightly modified).

While analyzing the work done in all sections of Chapter 5, we recognize the relevance of all four elements. In case studies, the used template and interview guides took into account the relations between actors, the control and power balances between them, the boundary conditions, and the orchestration actions; the latter where observed within a relatively simple partnership as well as within partnerships of partnerships. Even for FOODPathS, as a mini-partnership of networks, this holds. In Mirror Groups, it has been highlighted that the 'often forgotten groups' – playing key roles in our global food systems should be listened to and actively involved in a fair power-balanced way. In the scenario workshop, all partners considered the consequences of societal and planetary challenges for potential, future, food system governance models. If a single actor likes to join forces with others, it is of key relevance to understand how each actor may fit in different future scenarios. This allows the most effective orchestration of joint activities.

This generic governance model describes the four main elements of the governance of food systems striving to reach sustainability, hence of any kind of partnership. Thus, it should also serve as a fundament under the governance architecture of a European Partnership that has been presented in Section 5.2 and Figure XX. Only 'orchestration' (point 4 in Figure XX) is less apparent in that figure. This is related to fine-tuning activities between multiple partnerships of different sizes, configurations, scales of operations, contexts, etc. This is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. The Orchestration of multiple partnerships to contribute to sustainability. In this figure, all Partnerships are different in 'sizes', but have a similar architecture to facilitate orchestration ('ideal situation'). However, in reality architectures may be completely different.

7. References

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8. Timeline

The start of thinking about governance models by FOODPathS partners already started in mid-2021 while preparing the Narrative of the Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (P-SFS). Since then, several elements of partnership governance have been elaborated, in particular also in the FOODPathS project. Key steps are presented in the table below:

Date	Topic	Who involved	Reference
June 2021	Narrative of the P-SFS, with a dedicated session on governance	INRAE, AU, FZJ, ICLEI,..	https://scar-europe.org/images/FOOD/Main_actions/Food-Systems-Partnership_Narrative-06-2021.pdf
April 2022	Template of the P-SFS, complementary remarks about governance	INRAE, AU, FZJ, ICLEI,..	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-04/ec_rtd_he-partnership-sustainable-food-systems-april_2022.pdf
Jan 2023	SRIA of the P-SFS, with a section on governance and R&I theme 'change the way we govern'	INRAE, AU, FDE, FZJ,..	https://scar-europe.org/images/FOOD/Main_actions/SFS_Partnership_SRIA_31012023.pdf
June 2022 – Nov 2024	Kick-off of FOODPathS with work on FS cases (including governance studies and in-depth case studies)	WP4 & WP7 teams	Deliverable D2.1; https://www.foodpaths.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Deliverable-2.1-Mapping-results-fv_compressed.pdf
June 2023	Workshop on Governance and scenarios	All partners	Section 5.5
Jan-Nov 2024	Systematic literature review of FS governance for sustainability	INRAE	https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x
2024	Mirror Group Events	ICLEI, WP7 team	FOODPathS ; https://www.foodpaths.eu/news-item/insights-from-the-first-foodpaths-mirror-group-meeting/ ; https://www.foodpaths.eu/in-action/partnership-inclusivity/

9. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following table presents the results of work related to this Deliverable 2.6 (N.A. = not applicable for this Deliverable 2.6). This is done per the KPI category, as defined in the Description of Activities (DoA) of FOODPathS. The stated targets in the DoA are defined for the end of the FOODPathS project, hence for Month 42.

No.	KPI category	Main KPIs with obtained results	Target*
Out-come #1	Aligned governance & Commitment	(i) level of political & financial commitment to EU, national & local actions: N.A. (ii) percentage of committed EU countries and funding agencies: N.A. (iii) inclusiveness via a number of other co-funders (private, regional,..): in the workshop and world café session WP2, all partners have participated. The review of food systems governance for sustainability was not foreseen in the DoA; its publication is above expectations.	20+
Out-come #2	Shared visions and actions	(i) level of partner's commitment to a common mission, vision, and strategy: All partners participated in (i) the development of scenarios for governance models and priority settings of their network organization, (ii) the world café session on WP2, governance, and case studies. (ii) perceived inclusiveness of the governance model by actors: This indicator will become relevant while elaborating the Manual; for this manual, the main outcome 'new conceptual framework' will be discussed and amended. (iii) percentage of coherently presented best practices: There are 12 different governance architectures collected and synthesized in this deliverable (this is above the number of co-funded partnerships in cluster 6). In addition, four in-depth case studies have been performed that target governance models at different scales > 4 more than initially foreseen.	100% 100%
Out-come #3	Mutual Benefits by strengthening local FS actions	(i) a number of culturally-specific priorities included in funders strategy: N.A. (ii) number of functional FS Labs demonstrated by FOODPathS: In WP4&2, this number is in total 7, out of which 4 are here described in detail; the others will be reported by WP4. The WP7 cases are detailed in their Deliverables. (iii) percentage of exemplary cases with trade-offs: This will be communicated via WP7	15 4 <25%,

It should be noted that for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation, WP-specific material indicators will be reported in WP8 deliverables.

Finally, as stated in the Description of Activities (DoA), this project can only provide information for categorized sets of **KPIs with indicative Targets** (a percentage level or fixed number) which are all evolving from 0 at the start of the project⁴.

⁴ In a R&I project, KPI can be set for e.g. reduction of waste thanks to the actions carried out in a project. In this CSA, preparing a prototype Partnership, KPI are harder to define since there is no reference line at its start.

10. Conclusions and next steps

The main conclusions of our work are that a novel conceptual framework for Partnerships on Sustainable Food Systems could be developed, that integratively describes four key elements of governance: (i) interactions between actors, (ii) control and power balances, (iii) (in)formal rules, ... and (iv) orchestration of FS activities to reach sustainable outcomes.

Our work on food system cases reveals that all four elements are relevant in the studied cases. However, more discussions about its use are needed in the final project year. This also holds for the work on mirror groups, and legislative measures. The collection of governance architectures reveals key building blocks of governance architectures of a variety of partnerships, however, does not always elucidate the functioning of governance. An example is that inclusivity is often stated, but not presented in the core processes in partnerships. One exception seems to be Circular-biobased Europe, in which a variety of actors are key stakeholders (and co-funders) of partnership activities. Here, future work may better clarify this.

This Deliverable does not yet include the considerations about funding strategies and forums, observatories, links between education, policy and R&I, a sustainability chart, etc. This will be part of the final FOODPathS Deliverable D2.7 'Manual Partnership, final version'.

ANNEX I – Overview of governance architectures of Partnerships and Joint Initiatives

Below a series of governance architectures of Partnerships and large joint initiatives are presented that are used in the analysis in Section 5.2.

Disclaimer: the here presented architectures may be changed in time due to the further developments of each partnership.

EU Partnership: BIODIVERSITY (BIODIVERSA+)

Source:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/european_partnership_for_research_biodiversity_to_safeguard_life_on_earth.pdf (see page 38)

Figure 16: Possible governance structure for the Biodiversity Partnership. Three levels of engagement of stakeholders will be used: (i) engagement with a broad range of stakeholders through the Stakeholder Board, allowing two-way exchanges and information and mobilization of a large number of stakeholders; (ii) higher involvement of a range of stakeholders for surveying the activities of the Partnership and providing advices; and (iii) direct collaboration with a few major stakeholders (when relevant through establishment of sub-contracts).

EU Partnership: BLUE ECONOMY

Source: presentation given during the workshop on 3rd March 2021, online; https://www.jpi-oceans.eu/sites/jpi-oceans.eu/files/managed/Publications%20files/Sustainable%20Blue%20Economy%20Partnership_Presentation_Feb%202021_Public.pdf

Schematic of a governance architecture

Figure from proposal, July 2020

EU Partnership: ASSESSMENT OF RISK FROM CHEMICALS (PARC)

Source: Draft proposal: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnerships-chemical-risk-assessment.pdf (see pages: 54, 56, and 58)

Figure 9: Strategic Governance (green) and its interface with the Partnership management (blue)

EU Partnership WATER4ALL

Source: <https://www.water4all-partnership.eu/governance-structure>

The Partnership Governance will rely on:

- A decision-making body, the Governing Board (GB), composed of representatives of each Partnership member which are those committing to the partnership vision and SRIA and are financially committing to the partnership actions to be granted within the EC partnership agreement;
 - o The GB deals with the global strategy, and the related implementation plan and defines the policy rules (e.g. voting rules, integration of new partners, ...).
 - o They will appoint a chair and vice-chair(s) for chairing the different partnership governance boards and representing the Partnership as necessary.
 - o They will also elect two GB members to sit on the Executive Board.
 - o They will serve to connect national communities and actors (e.g. via national mirror groups), enhance closer involvement of the local/regional and national actors (policymakers, operators, research and innovation communities ...), and ensure better matchmaking to their concrete needs.
- An Executive Board (EB), which implements the strategy defined and issued by the GB and monitors the advancements of the Partnership activities. The EB will be responsible for regularly checking the implementation of the GB decisions and preparing recommendations for GB review and consideration. The EB will be comprised of i) the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the Partnership; ii) the Partnership members coordinating Pillars; iii) additional members based upon expressions of interest and approved by the GB; and iv) if necessary, task leaders or associated partners board members to discuss specific issues. It's proposed to have two additional GB members associated on a volunteer basis to enlarge GB involvement and to have the participation of the Associated Partners board as observers.
- The Partnership Coordination Team (PCT), which will ensure the day-to-day operational management of the Partnership activities, in particular, efficient coordination between the different bodies and supporting the exchanges between them. It will also be in charge of communication and support in assisting the Partnership members with the implementation of Partnership activities.
 - o It should comprise experienced staff hired by one or several Partnership members on behalf of the consortium.
 - o It will also take care of monitoring key issues such as GDPR, Ethics, Gender balance, ...
- An Associated Partners Board, for all institutions committing to specific actions and will join via MoU with the Partnership consortium
 - o As some partners could not join the Partnership (cf. EC eligibility conditions), they will be associated via this board, allowing the participation of a broad range of actors

- o The role of the Common Implementation Strategy Group will be key at this level.
- An Advisory Board with Scientific and Stakeholders representatives, which advises and makes recommendations on the overall strategy, the main activities of the Partnership, and possible cooperation with other initiatives of relevance. They also serve as the key means for further communication/dissemination to different stakeholder communities (researchers, policymakers, economic sectors ...) to interact with the Water4All Partnership.
 - o It will also include representatives of the thematic DGs and international experts to ensure a link to international important fora.
 - o The role of the Common Implementation Strategy Group will be detailed with exchanges with DG ENV.

PRIMA MED Partnership

Source: <https://prima-med.org/who-we-are/inside-prima/>

BBI Biobased Industry Consortium (now CBE-JU)

Source: <https://www.cbe.europa.eu/system/files?file=2022-12/BBI%20JU%20Driving%20Europe%E2%80%99s%20green%20transition.pdf>

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE
Advisory body

15 independent experts selected by the Governing Board.

Responsibilities

Provide essential scientific advice on the priorities in the annual work plans and the achievements outlined in the annual activity report.

PROGRAMME OFFICE
Manages the BBI JU programme and ensures implementation of the partnership

23-strong team grouped into three units.

Responsibilities

Manage and oversee all aspects of the operation (call management and programme monitoring, administration, financial management, legal control, human resources, and communication).

'The BBI JU is a good example of an initiative covering every stage of the scientific process, from fundamental science to technological development and innovation, leading to new products coming to market.'

MEP **Maria da Graça Carvalho** is a member of the European Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy and a former Portuguese Minister of Science, Innovation and Higher Education.

EXECUTIVE OFFICE

Responsibilities

General management, audit, internal, and legal control;

Communication relations with public and private sector stakeholders;

Ensure BBI JU activities respect the Horizon 2020 standards, the EU's research and innovation programme, and its principles of transparency and openness.

PROGRAMME UNIT

Responsibilities

Organise and implement the calls for proposals. Managing proposals including quality, likely impact, and potential for addressing the stated challenges.

Carry out a thorough lifecycle analysis of the projects including, processes, products, outputs, KPIs, mid-term assessment, and financial status.

ADMINISTRATION AND FINANCE UNIT

Responsibilities

Safeguard BBI JU's financial interests and ensure the fiscal operations were properly carried out;

Provide the tools needed for the BBI JU to deliver on its mission whilst ensuring an effective use of resources in all activities.

EIT FOOD

Source: EIT Food Strategic Agenda 2018 – 2024– Making innovation happen

https://www.eitfood.eu/media/documents/EIT-StrategicAgenda-Booklet-A4-Final_disclaimer.pdf 'Section 2.1.2 EIT Food governance structures – page 15)

Figure 5: EIT Food Governance

JPI Healthy Diets for Healthy Living

Source: https://www.zonmw.nl/sites/zonmw/files/typo3-migrated-files/Leaflet_JPI_HDHL_Progress_Update.pdf

JPI HDHL Governance Structure

JPI FACCE

No Figure is available, but the following text description describes the governance structure:

'The governance structure consists of a decision-making [Governing Board \(GB\)](#) and two advisory boards, the [Scientific Advisory Board \(SAB\)](#) and [Stakeholder Advisory Board \(StAB\)](#). These boards are supported by a [Secretariat](#).

The Governing Board comprises one or two high-level representatives from each of the 24 participating countries who are willing to actively contribute to and participate in JPI operations.

The representatives are typically from research or agriculture ministries, research funding organizations, or major research performing organizations that have the authority to take strategic decisions and engage resources from national research funds.'

ERANET SUSFOOD2

Source: <https://susfood-db-era.net/main/Governance-structure-SUSFOOD2-Cofund>

EJP RARE DISEASES

Source: https://www.eitfood.eu/media/documents/EIT-StrategicAgenda-Booklet-A4-Final_disclaimer.pdf

- Keep it simple and define clear distinctions of responsibilities between different bodies (GA, ExCom, Operating Group)
- If not involved directly, engage with policy makers (ministries, EC, representatives of industry and society) through an external body. Policy Board + National Mirror Groups
- If implementing open calls for projects make sure to have a “fire-wall” process and independent Board of Funders and Scientific/Advisory Board
- Make sure that you have a transparent decision-making process, even if sometimes it may require “procedural” validation (the coordinator should not decide in the name of the consortium)

GLOBAL GOVERNANCE OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE (AMR) – A ONE-HEALTH APPROACH

Source: https://www.who.int/antimicrobial-resistance/interagency-coordination-group/IACG_Future_global_governance_for_AMR_120718.pdf (see p. 9)

Global Governance for Antimicrobial Resistance

ANNEX 2 – Governance sections of the narrative, template and SRIA of the P-SFS

Governance structure of the Partnership from the NARRATIVE

A possible governance structure of the partnership is described in Figure 3 (in the main text with further descriptions of its building blocks), including a **Governing board (GB)**, **Management board (MB)**, **EU Food systems Executive Office (FSEO)**, **EU Food Systems Hub of Hubs (FSHH)**, **Collaboration Partners Platform (CPP)**, and **Advisory board (AB)**.

It should be noted that the further elaboration of the Governance structure in the template would include a reflection on the most suitable governance structure for a mission-driven approach to the Partnership. It should include reflections on a potential role for the SCAR Food Systems Strategic Working Group, which is the convening platform for co-creating the Partnership. Also, a comparison of different governance models is then recommended.

Co-funded Partnership on Safe and Sustainable Food Systems

To speed up the Food System transition the involvement of all relevant stakeholders is necessary. The **Partnership on Safe and Sustainable Food Systems** will be a co-funded partnership where the co-fund owners and the EC are considered as the first circle of partners to finance activities of the Partnership. However, the following elements should be taken into account for commitment and alignment of all relevant stakeholders: (i) the possibility for in-kind contributions from both private and public stakeholders, (ii) the flexibility in programming, and (iii) long-term implementation frameworks.

The advantages of the Co-funded Partnership model include the direct involvement of the European Commission (EC), direct benefits in terms of mobilized national funding being co-funded, and the possibility to design and implement a common program *within* the Member States/Associated Countries, thus mobilizing even more national R&I funding under a jointly programmed Partnership. This is an attractive and proven model that has served well in a large number of JPIs and ERA-NETs⁵ experiences show modalities are possible to include private partners. For the private sector, contributing to sustainability goals is an important source of legitimacy and a driver of innovation, not to speak of mitigation of reputation and liability risks related to environmental or social hazards. Moreover, **a well-structured balanced, and sustained interaction between the private sector the public sector, and societal actors on R&I policy can contribute to highlighting the critical points of present and future regulation and help identify potential barriers to implementation.**

Traditionally, farmers' representatives have had a strong influence on the definition of the agricultural policy agenda. But when it comes to food systems, it is important to recognize that retailing and processing have a key role as intermediaries between production and consumption. **The alignment of private goals and public goals is thus a condition for the success of public strategies. In particular innovative food businesses implementing the European Green Deal and Farm to Fork objectives could play a lighthouse role.** Governance of partnerships should then be able to guarantee a balance between all interests (small and big, different phases of the chain, different sectors, geographical differences), and should be based on a clear commitment of the private sector to common values, to public goals and the related targets.

Therefore, one aim is to find loci and leverage points⁶ in food systems, where specific changes by conscious actors may create positive feedback from other actors in the system, resulting in transformations that catalyze co-benefits and synergies between healthy diets, behavioral change, and circular and affordable food production, processing and marketing with low waste and with sustainable outcomes. Such successful changes will require food systems inspired by research, innovation, and real-life experiments and demonstrators. Hence, the Partnership will benefit if it can identify: (i) the nodes where we as a part of the system on the societal level are underperforming and (ii) provide opportunities to **incredible partners** who can make a difference.

⁵ <https://www.era-learn.eu/partnerships-in-a-nutshell/type-of-networks/partnerships-under-horizon-2020>

⁶ Meadows, D. (1999). Leverage points: Places to intervene in a system. Hartland, WI: The Sustainability Institute.

Commitment to stakeholders' involvement in the spirit of responsible research and innovation (RRI) in all stages of the Partnership (including the agenda setting) and consequent responsibility should be at the basis of any governance model.

Progress monitoring and the Exit Strategy

The Strategies developed under the Green Deal, first of all, the Farm to Fork and the Biodiversity strategies, identify precise and ambitious targets and **pledge to monitor the progress towards them**. The time frame of the Partnership instrument is restricted concerning its activities. However, its remit and subsequent challenges are likely to exist well-beyond the lifespan of a network. A European Food System Observatory for performance monitoring is likely to stay important well after Horizon Europe. Activities of the Partnership would gradually give shape to and be sustained by, a Mission on Food Systems. It is relevant to work on the coordinated framework with the Agroecology Partnership and other relevant initiatives (Eurobarometer action, Risk-assessment of chemicals, Digitalisation, EIT-Food) through joint meetings, common forums, coordination among SRIAs, and possible joint calls.

Potential impact

The **Potential impact** of the partnership is strongly related to the **capacity to align actors** of the food system around the goals identified by the Green Deal and to quantify contributions to the objectives in the Farm to fork strategy. Besides, it should have qualified contributions to food and nutrition security, safety, efficient resource usage and economic and social aspects in food system approaches at EU, national, regional, and local levels. **Its success depends on the transformation capacity of food system actors** towards more sustainable outcomes, via understanding food systems, exploring system approaches, searching for appropriate leverage points and solutions, and overcoming barriers and trade-offs. For this reason, the **impact will be assessed in terms of conceptual development** (capacity to introduce new concepts in the knowledge ecosystem), **technology development** (capacity to deliver technological solutions tailored to the variety of emerging problems and to foster their market uptake), **social and business development** (capacity to provide knowledge to new social configurations, new business models and bottom-up initiatives), **policy development** (capacity to embody new concepts and new technological solutions into policies), and **territorial and context-specific 'RIPE'⁷ activities**.

The **success factors, or better 'Key Performance Indicators (KPI)'**, are highly diverse and, thus, categorized. The categories, with one concrete KPI as an example, are (i) *commitment of stakeholders* (level of **political and financial commitment**), (ii) *contributions to more sustainable food system pathways* (level of **change towards a systems approach**), (iii) *relevant focus areas in safe and sustainable food systems* (potential of a **focus area to establish leverage points**), (iv) *alignment of activities at EU level* (level of **monitored alignment of European and national R&I efforts**), (v) *mutual benefits by strengthening local food system activities* (quality of the **network of FS-labs** in terms of exchanging best practices and co-funded actions), (vi) *performance of Partnership activities* (**programming structure** for management of calls and 'RIPE' agenda setting), (vii) *attractiveness and source of inspiration (via interactive communication) of the Partnership* (level of **spirit, joint ambition, belonging to** and engagement based on realistic success stories).

⁷ RIPE = Research & Innovation & Policy making & Education.

Drafting group 2:

Governance described in the TEMPLATE

- Outline the governance and management of the Partnership, including advisory structures and mechanisms to be established. Demonstrate how the governance and management of the Partnership helps to achieve the defined vision and objectives. Describe how it will contribute to ensuring coherence and synergies with the EU research and innovation landscape and demonstrate, as well as transparency and openness during the Partnership as regards the identification of its objectives, priorities, vision, Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), and work programs.
- Provide, with the support of the Commission services supporting the preparation, a description of the involvement of the Commission in the preparation and implementation of the Partnership. In particular, describe the mechanisms for defining and defending the EU public interest in the framework of the Partnership.

The governance structure of the Partnership:

To guide the Transition towards safe and Sustainable Food Systems as the new Partnership, the governance structure should be inclusive and capable of aligning strategies, as well as agendas and work programs. Even more, it should be structured in such a way that the 4 thematic areas will be successfully implemented and operationalized. Finally, it should guarantee a coherent and systematic way of operating and addressing the 4 inter-connected activities. Consequently, a possible governance structure of the partnership considers:

- **Governing board (GB):** the highest-level decision-making body. Will be formed by partners representing program owners across Europe and from the European Commission. It should also ensure that both macro and place-based priorities are considered.
- **Management board (MB):** will support the GB and is responsible for day-to-day management, initiating and overseeing the Partnerships' activities. Will include the coordinator, co-coordinator, and hub leaders.
- **EU Food Systems Executive Office (FSEO):** will implement the defined actions according to the established work plans, performing the R&I activities and establishing an interface between science and policy. FSEO will be constituted by the Hub leaders, Task leaders, and Partners.
- **EU Food Systems Hub of Hubs (FSHH):** will consider the national hubs (NH) and thematic hubs (TH), which will closely interact with the Collaboration Partners Platform (CPP).
 - **National hubs (NH):** national networking bodies regarding the thematic of the partnership, gathering the national expertise on these subjects and federating/framing relevant initiatives at local and regional levels.
 - **Thematic hubs (TH):** transnational hubs dedicated to specific subjects/common themes under the umbrella of the partnership, corresponding to "system thinking hubs".
- **Collaboration Partners Platform (CPP)/Ambassadors:** should include the representatives of the different actors playing a role in the definition and implementation of safe and sustainable food systems. CPP will consider the Food Systems Community of Practice, Private Partners, and Representatives of diverse civil society and other stakeholder groups such as industry. A youth group or youth ambassador system should be part of it.
- **Advisory board (AB):** provides advice to the MB on the planning and implementation of the main activities of the partnership.

It should be noted that further elaboration of the Governance structure in the template would include a reflection on the most suitable governance structure for a mission-driven approach to the Partnership, which may ensure that over time the portfolio of projects funded through competitive calls will cover as much of the SRIA and Roadmap as possible and that results (outputs) from individual projects feed into the necessary outcomes in terms of Safe and sustainable food systems following an explicit impact pathway. This means the R&I solutions aim to respond to the grand food system challenges holistically and systemically: economic, environmental, and societal solutions require horizontal collaboration. It should include reflections on a potential role for the SCAR Food Systems Strategic Working Group, which is the convening platform for co-creating the Partnership. Moreover, a comparison of different governance models is then recommended.

The role of and interactions with different stakeholders as described in the SRIA of the P-SFS

The potential impact of the partnership is strongly related to the capacity to align actors of food systems around goals. The first condition for success is that a wide diversity of actors join forces in a partnership. Therefore, interactions with different stakeholders are sought.

As recently published by the consortium of FOODPathS (2022), the following stakeholder groups can be distinguished:

- (v) The '**Partners of the P-SFS Consortium**', essentially consist of partners from ministries and funding agencies, however all others who will sign the P-SFS-Grant with the EC, like regions, associated partners, private sector actors, etc.

- (vi) **The ‘Applicants of P-SFS Funding’**, are the actors that apply for grants delivered via open calls by the P-SFS Consortium.
- (vii) **The ‘Potential future Partnership SFS Consortium’**, grouping actors that are jointly willing to guarantee the continuation of the Partnership during and **after** the 7-year grant provided by the EC.
- (viii) **The ‘wider public’** are actors that are benefiting from the sustainability impact created by the Partnership and provide feedback to the Partners or Applicants in one way or the other.

Next to these stakeholder groups, other key players will be approached interactively. They should be capable of translating findings from the P-SFS into actions, but inversely also contribute with their experiences, competences, recommendations, and open questions to the further development of the P-SFS. A specific interface – strongly linked to the knowledge hubs (Activity C) – needs thus be developed that guides the information flows in both directions. It also should be able to keep track of communication, dissemination, exploitation, and demonstration actions (Activity D). Key examples of intervening stakeholder groups will be:

- Relevant networks at all scales, in particular the ones in the FOODPathS consortium who are active from local (e.g. ICLEI, MilanFoodPact, also others in Driving Urban Transitions), regional (ERIAFF, and related 3S Platforms), national (united via ERANETs Susfood and CoreOrganic, JPI HDHL, National Food Technology Platforms Food for Life, ..), EU-wide (like SCAR FS SWG, BIOEAST, Mission Boards, FoodDrinkEurope, CopaCogeca, Confagricoltura, EFFoST, ISEKI, ETPs, but later also others like EJPs, European Enterprise Network, Policy Evaluation Network, BEUC, IFOAM Organic Europe, Research federations, Green ERA-Hub, Social Movements like SlowFood, Food Waste Movement, European Food Banks, etc.) to global levels (ICLEI World Secretariat and OnePlanet Network and later also others, see below). They all serve to substantially enlarge the impact of P-SFS actions via enrolling (like a snowball) best and worst practices throughout their networks;
- National mirror groups, who are guiding the nationally involved partners and applicants in their SFS actions by seeking synergies, highlighting unique contributions, etc. at micro, meso, and macro levels;
- An inter-connected network of these national mirror groups, to exchange insights and assessments between countries in terms of multi-(interacting)-actor approaches, inter-disciplinary and –sector strategies.
- EC JRCs and EFSA, who provide expertise to the P-SFS Consortium in terms of safety regulations, data monitoring, and analysis, science-to-policy recommendations, etc.;
- Experts and expert organizations, who will continuously provide the latest insights to the Consortium about the complexity of FS and FS approach; this also includes representatives of connected sector organizations like the EIT Food, Health, Climate, and Digital as well as the CBE-JU for addressing potential resources competition for non-food uses.
- Civil society organizations, including social partners, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and grassroots organizations, serve general interests and mediation roles between parties. Exchanges with the European Economic and Social Committee will be regularly sought;
- Global institutions, give feedback on potential trade-offs, in particular regarding developing countries, and co-benefits, both for developing and developed countries globally.
- Philanthropic organizations (as already united in FOODPathS), sharing their supported case studies called ‘unusual suspect initiatives’ and possibly co-funding targeted P-SFS activities;
- Financers, investing in short and long-term sustainability-oriented activities wherever possible;
- Media in the broadest sense, for local to global communication in different forms.
- Last, but not least, Citizens, and Consumer organizations, reveal their appreciation (or not) of activities, and join participatory actions; the endless number of target groups requires some categorization.

The prioritization for collaboration topics in different regions will recurrently be done under the SRIA of the P-SFS; the policy commitment to the shared R&I agenda of key regions is crucial. Here, the National Food Technology Platforms will play a catalyzing role. This includes the EU’s associated countries in the South Eastern and Eastern regions of Europe and Africa.

In addition, international cooperation is foreseen with Europe’s priority partner countries and regions on the manifold cross-border dimensions of Europe’s food systems. Key pertinent dimensions are 1) building capacities for monitoring the sustainability of FS, 2) global research programming around external dimensions of Europe’s Green transition, and 3) regional and global science-policy interfaces on FS. Here, the P-SFS will join forces

with organizations like the FAO, UNFSS, PRIMA (Mediterranean focus), EU-Africa Partnership, CGIAR, WHO, UNEP, UNICEF, WFP, GAIN, WEF, Global Young academy, etc. to support food security, fight against increasing hunger and respond to the question of ‘how to feed 10 billion people in 2050 in a sustainable way?’.

For Africa, as a strategic cooperation partner, the EU seeks to support actions targeted to finding locally adapted solutions to challenges that are global, but which often hit Africa hardest. Green transition is one of the pillars of the European and African EU-AU Innovation Agenda, tackling education, research, and innovations. To encourage international collaboration on these challenges, it is envisaged that the Africa-Europe International Research Consortium (IRC) for Food and Nutrition Security and Sustainable Agriculture (FNSSA) will be aligned with the P-SFS and that African challenges are considered in its SRIA. The IRC was launched in 2022 as a long-term partnership of government institutions, research funders, and research partners in the EU and Africa, building on EU-funded Coordination programs like ProIntens Africa (2015-2017) and LEAP4FNSSA (2018-2022).

Finally, the notion that the transition to SFS only may be achieved together with the seven other Partnerships in Cluster 6 of HE, requires regular exchanges and a well-founded cooperation scheme. Consequently, the above-listed key players may be consulted for issues surpassing the P-SFS.

SRIA, the thematic Area 4 ‘Change the way we govern’

Subtitle: *Leverage points for local, national, EU, and global transition pathways, co-creation, including private ones like the Farm to Fork code of conduct & local initiatives (e.g. cities)*

This thematic area targets research and innovation needs in the governance of food systems. It doesn’t target the governance of partnerships itself, however, it **may provide new insights that will become relevant for the governance of the partnership itself**. Examples are the understanding and new knowledge on roles and power balances of different actors (targeting inclusivity), and governance challenges over different scales (and different actors involved).

Status

The Food2030 pathways for action state that *“The many challenges related to Food Systems (FS), as well as their key impact on climate, sustainability, health, and livelihoods, have made clear that we urgently need to improve our FS governance beyond today’s predominantly fragmented and sectoral approach”* (EC, 2020).

‘Governance’ describes *“the characteristic processes by which society defines and handles its problems”* (Voss et al., 2006). It is the result of the interactions of many actors with different problems, goals, and strategies. Governance therefore also involves conflicting interests and struggle for power. This R&I Area aims to contribute to improving knowledge of governance patterns and governance evolution and provide solutions that can steer food systems toward sustainability. Issues related to governance are fragmentation and slowness to change, difficulties in keeping the urgency of the problem high on the political agenda, and difficulties in handling the complexity of FS (EC, 2020).

Research on governance starts from the recognition of already existing initiatives in the public, private, and civil society sectors.

In the public domain, the Green Deal raises the issue of how to integrate policies of different administration sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, health, food safety, environment, and internal market, and to what degree policies may and should be harmonized across scales (the EU, the National, and regional/municipal levels of administrations).

In the private domain, food industry actors have implemented sustainability strategies that imply assessment, data collection, and appropriate governance patterns (Toussaint et al. 2021; Brunori et al., 2016). They are implemented through corporate responsibility, food standards, labeling, traceability, certifications, and many other initiatives. However, many companies are concerned with the costs of transition and may tend to resist change. At the same time, concentration in the food industry and the influence of powerful lobbies raise concerns about fairness and equity.

In the civil society domain, the engagement of citizens in local food systems (CSA, etc.) and in cooperative business models (production, retail) is a driver for change as it contributes to breaking the sectoral barriers and fosters system thinking by focusing on problems.

Moreover, the importance of trade raises attention to the connections with extra-EU system components, as policy internal decisions and governance patterns affect actors and activities outside the EU.

In the Farm to Fork strategy, the Commission has planned several initiatives related to food. These are among others a Legislative framework for sustainable food systems (EC, 2022c.), actions in the fields of food loss and waste prevention (EC, 2021d.), the EU Code of Conduct on Responsible Food Business and Marketing Practices (EC, 2022f.), measures for sustainable food consumption and production, the Proposal for a Directive on corporate sustainability due diligence (EC, 2022g.), and the taxonomy for sustainable finance (EC, 2022i.)⁸. If properly coordinated, these policies can become powerful drivers of transformation.

Being transformation an open process, full of barriers, trade-offs, and conflicting interests at stake, research will have to support it by improving the capacity of policymaking to frame the problems, design effective policy tools, to assess their impact, to foster participation, to encourage experiments and to learn from them, and to make timely, evidence- and consensus-based decisions.

Governance is key to effective policy design and implementation. The research will have to provide knowledge on how to better coordinate the actors that populate food systems and align their actions around sustainability goals. It will have also to study how governance will evolve with the involvement of new actors such as municipalities, grassroots movements, and digital platforms.

In 2015, many European cities committed themselves to building SFS in the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. In the cities adhering to the Pact, experiments on local food policies are being carried out. Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe have supported the process of networking between municipalities to exchange knowledge on the implementation of local food policies. The project Fit4Food2030 (Fit4Food, 2022) has provided input to a policy framework, a review of food-related policies in Europe, targeted responsible research and innovation (RRI), and developed tools for the transformation of FS. The JPI HDHP (2019) supported Policy Evaluation Network has developed tools for assessing the effectiveness of policies and regulations concerning food and nutrition and has developed a monitoring tool for assessing the implementation of policies across Europe, i.e. the Food Environment Policy Index.

How will R&I 4 contribute to the impact pathways and the Intervention Logic?

The partnership, through its interconnected activities (Activity Area 'A') synthesized via the FS observatory (Activity Area 'B'), and the living labs knowledge hub (Activity Area 'C'), will increase the understanding of the actors in public and private governance of FS, their interdependence and evolution, their relative power and their transformative potential vis-à-vis sustainable FS objectives. The theme will contribute to the assessment and comparison of the performance of different governance patterns around food at the local, national, and EU level, in synergy with the Farm to Fork monitoring framework. Research in this field will also co-design and facilitate the assessment of experiments of food policy governance at the local level. This will support the implementation of R&I Areas 1, 2, and 3 since improved (understanding of) governance can shape the drivers of FS sustainability, as in the case of the 'food environment'.

Knowledge gaps to be addressed

The key knowledge gap to be addressed is how society and policymaking are organized concerning food, and what are the strengths and weaknesses of different governance arrangements. The P-SFS aims at understanding how public and private governance in an FS view can improve the capacity of system actors to **appraise** the system (its actors and activities, the barriers, trade-offs, and leverage points to transformation). Linked to this aim is a need to assess the performance of food systems (FS observatory, Activity 'B'). Moreover, the P-SFS aims at increasing actors' **commitment** to sustainability. Linked to this aim is a need to support local food policy experiments, study the effectiveness of corporate responsibility strategies, assess the uptake of sustainability standards, improve the participation of citizens in corporate decisions, to encourage the full integration of agroecology into food systems (Activity 'C').

⁸ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en

About **appraisal**, effective policies need consistent representations of the systems and useful data to monitor their state and evolution, and to identify emerging risks. This is imperative for a clearer understanding of FS, for a shared vision of SFS, and for policy coherence.

In the **public domain**, it is now understood that separate policy sectors generate different bodies of knowledge that are not consistent with each other and often tend to address emerging problems with inappropriate knowledge instruments. The research in this field regards how policy problems are framed, the level of consensus about the problems, the level of agreement of existing knowledge, and how the production of knowledge about them is affected by the interaction between different types of actors.

In the **private domain**, appraisal is key to value creation, as successful communication of the sustainability performance of processes and products can be translated into commercial value. Moreover, appraisal is a necessary condition for accountability towards the community. For this reason, from the sustainability perspective, methodologies, quality of data, choice of indicators, disclosure of data, participation of all actors to priority setting, and communication must be subject to common rules that avoid deception and build trust. More participation can also balance the influence of powerful lobbies. Research should aim here to substantially improve the transparency of the system.

In the **civil society domain**, access to information, participation in knowledge production, and 'voice' on decisions are keys to policy processes. Access to information can empower civil society organizations to raise issues, to have a stake in the agenda setting, and to control the processes of implementation.

Research can contribute to improving societal **commitment** to SFS by addressing common problems, encouraging multi-actor dialogues, and leading the co-construction of sustainable solutions to the problems of FS. Transition requires the participation of all actors, improved coordination between sectors (agriculture and fisheries, food-health-social-environment, sustainability-security-safety), between operations in the value chain (production/processing/retailing), between levels (local-national-EU- global), between functions (science, policy, civil society), and between scientific disciplines. There is a need to co-create governance solutions that can improve coordination and initiatives that can foster integration between policies.

R&I needs to explore how private and public actors, networks, and institutions can be involved in governance with an FS view and committed to transformation. As food policies have no jurisdiction in many member states, there is a need to identify 'institutional entrepreneurs' who can lead the change through leverage points, where policy initiatives may create large shifts in overall governance in private and civil society domains leading to SFS outcomes.

In the **public sector**, the key issue is how to align different policy levels (national, regional, local) and different policy domains around shared goals in a coherent food system planning. To improve the speed and the coherence of transformation, new actors and new fora where issues are debated and coordination is fostered are necessary. Municipalities and local administrations have shown increasing activism in this field. Given the variety of the actors and the issues, however, there are no one-size-fits-all solutions, and experiments need to be activated and assessed.

In the **private sector**, several governance styles are emerging. Power relations within the supply chain have strong implications for the distribution of value. The landscape of the actors of the European FS is changing due to innovation processes and market trends. Corporate strategies range between further globalization and relocalization; some of them look increasingly to create value for the local community, and to activate more intense relations with local administrations. Some of them exploit market mechanisms to reduce production costs, and others create partnerships with their suppliers. The role of intermediate bodies, such as Cooperatives and Farm Advisory services, is key to a healthy, efficient, and fair FS. What is their role in the new context emerging with the Green Deal? Can they provide leadership and entrepreneurship for the transformation of FS?

Civil Society has demonstrated to be a driver of change, as civil society actors raise sustainability issues to the public attention, act as watchdogs on the private sectors and public administrations, contribute to reframe discourses on food, and provide information about unexplored issues, are laboratories of FS transition experiments that promote innovative producers' / consumers patterns. Research on governance should study how civil society can provide entrepreneurship and leadership to promote transformative governance, and how availability and access to information (for example, concerning the true cost of food) could strengthen their role.

How will R&I Area 4 contribute to the overall aim of SFS via a Food systems approach?

R&I Area 4 will contribute to the improvement of the governance for SFS through research activities based on observation, comparison, and conceptual reflection of existing governance patterns in the public, private, and civil society domains. Research in this theme will be carried out mainly through research actions and stakeholder involvement and will rely to a great extent on living labs' activities, providing research questions, and organizing the processes of learning around these issues.

Research can combine retrospective studies that focus on causes, sources of pressure, and drivers; present-day sustainability assessments in different realms of the food system; and prospective studies that envision the future of food systems and advise measures and strategies to foster transitions towards more sustainable agri-food systems.

The partnership will study how to improve coordination between actors of the system, also considering the geographical differences (West-East, North-South, Rural-Urban). As governance is strongly related to knowledge creation, use, and communication, the P-SFS aims at creating knowledge ecosystems - involving diverse sources of knowledge - working actively to contribute to breaking the sectoral barriers and fostering policy coherence. The partnership will actively involve the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) and will actively pursue their integration with broader food-related knowledge systems, such as those related to marine policies, public health, environment.

Science-policy interfaces are key components of the new knowledge ecosystems. By improving communication between knowledge producers, users, and communicators, and by making sense of different knowledge, different values, and different interests, science-policy interfaces provide relevant, legitimate, and credible knowledge to address food-related policy problems. At the same time, science-policy interfaces can support scientific research to identify knowledge gaps. P-SFS will operate to develop science-policy interfaces at multiple levels.

The P-SFS will encourage - through strategy, guidelines, communication, and evaluation - all actors of knowledge ecosystems to work on policy and governance issues related to their domain of commitment. Through its observatory and the living labs, it will gather insights on best practices and barriers to change. Through FS-Labs, the partnership will also stimulate the actors of the system to experiment with innovative governance arrangements and the inclusion of new stakeholders. Moreover, the P-SFS will orchestrate the process of learning about these governance issues and mainstreaming them into regional and national policy instruments.

R&I&P questions to be answered in R&I Area 4

- What is the state and performance of existing governance of food systems in public respectively private domains vis-à-vis the challenges of transformation?
- How to foster joint understanding and coordination between normally divided sectors (land and sea, agro-food-health- social-environment), between levels (local-national-EU-global), and between functions (science, policy, business, and civil society) in an FS approach enabling policy coherence?
- What lessons can be learned from the comparison of governance patterns? What are the most promising governance patterns of food systems?
- What are the scientific principles of transformative FS governance? How can these principles be applied to public, private, and civil society-related governance patterns?
- What are the actors, the networks, and the institutions respectively in public, private, and civil society domains that can build a transformative FS governance and how do they operate?
- Which key governance initiatives in public, private, and civil society domains could act as leverage points in transforming FS?
- How will private governance adapt to the new food-related policies (public governance) planned with the Green Deal?
- How did governance with an FS approach evolve and did it enable desired transformations towards SFS?
- What are the actors, the networks, and the institutions that are endowed with leadership and entrepreneurship to build transformative Food System Governance, and how do they operate?

Requested enabling conditions

A partnership where all sectors and all actors have a voice, and where participation is balanced, can accelerate the adoption of a system approach. A strong relationship with policymakers in the above- mentioned policy fields will enable

them to focus on the relevant actions. A strong networking activity with all actors in the governance of food systems will ensure the circulation of information and coordination capacity.

Expected results

R&I Area 4 will contribute to deepening insights into the principles of transformative governance for sustainable food systems in public and private domains. The partnership will be itself an experiment of transformative governance, and research on R&I Area 4 will contribute to governance change and will contribute to policy making at different levels of the policy cycle.

Activities to carry out to achieve the expected results

The first set of Activities tries to respond to the R&I&P questions above by formulating R&I calls for funding within Activity 'A' focusing on understanding and experimenting with new governance patterns. Parts of the R&I activities may be carried out in FS- Labs and contribute to the knowledge hub (Activity Area 'C') and will feed into the FS observatory (Activity Area 'B').

In short, R&I Area 4 activities will produce evidence on transformative public and private governance and policy tools in an FS approach; assess governance coherence; identify leverage points, barriers, synergies, and trade-offs to the transformation of FS governance; develop assessment methods, guidelines for governance and improved science-policy interfaces.

ANNEX 3 Extraction of relevant governance issues from FOODPathS Deliverable D2.3 “Manual Prototype Partnership 1.0”

Observation 1: The larger the geographical scale of the partnership, the lower the number of categories of actors represented (I)

The geographical scale effect appears very clearly in the number of actors' categories represented and actively involved. Categories of actors are private (farmers, (artisanal) manufacturers, start-ups, SMEs, large nationals, multi-nationals...), public (local, regional, national, European, and global), academic, philanthropic, NGO, civil society, etc. The Milan Case (MC), a local initiative, is the most inclusive since it is the only one that also includes citizens next to all other categories. Then, the regional partnership Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM), serving the regional blue economy, gathers academic organizations, local NGOs and banks, and other public and private actors that are related to or impacted by blue economy activities. The national initiative Foodwest, being economically driven, represents companies, research, and a few public institutions. Finally, the cross-countries partnership BIOEAST includes two categories of actors: national ministries and academic organizations.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

Through the four in-depth case studies, a correlation appears between the geographical scale of the partnership and the number of categories of actors represented or actively involved. While lower-scale operating partnerships deal more with specific problems encountered by on-the-ground actors in their daily lives, larger-scale partnerships cover general objectives and are more focused on political, or sector-broad, decisions. For larger-scale partnerships, the complexity is further increased since it requires the active presence of a representative of a single category in each European country; sometimes, these representatives cannot even be identified since a thematic area is not defined (or e.g. more broadly formulated 'the bioeconomy')⁹. Still, then, it could evolve in time to widen the partnership, like for BIOEAST. For now, only research and politics are represented but it is planned that the private sector becomes involved in the future, due to its important role in innovations.

It should be noted that **the diversity of actors implies a diversity of opinions and ideas that could be potentially inspiring** and serve as a source of inspiration and innovation. On the other hand, **it increases considerably the number of partners and it could appear as a burden in terms of organizing activities**. The structuring of the organization of partnerships should, thus, get full attention, like the role of leaders at different levels of the organization (board of directors, thematic and task groups, communication, and technical/administration services). They ensure smooth communication throughout the network and ensure the mobilization of members around specific themes of 'partnership' activities.

Finally, the feeling of being a member of a collective initiative could also be considered as a threat that may spread among partners. For example, there is the **risk that a lonely driver attitude is created that** decreases the quality of common actions and decisions taken.

Observation 2: Every partnership is led by one actor's category in particular (II)

This observation is related to the context and history of the initiative, as well as to which actor launched the initial idea. In the case of MC, the Cariplo Foundation is considered as leading the MOU-signing process and follow-up activities, since they are strongly involved in the Milan Food Pack from the beginning. For PMM as well as for Foodwest, it concerns an initial request of companies for tools and services that help in reaching better stability, competitiveness, and sustainability outcomes. For BIOEAST, the lead is politically driven to reinforce bioeconomy activities in Central-Eastern Europe.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

As evoked in the section analysis above, the apparition of a leader is linked to the history of the partnership, its initial idea, and its commitment to reach – with all actors involved – the objectives that they have stated in the beginning. This holds for all four cases described here, in which a single organization took the lead.

⁹ This observation will require more discussion in the future. For example, one may argue to 'start small' and grow bigger - either on scale (e.g. Neighborhood scale is small, but stakeholder groups big) or participation (e.g. Few stakeholder groups at first and then add more categories). However, 'starting small and growing big' may evoke feelings of exclusion on the way - e.g., 'why weren't we included from the beginning?' and 'why should we come in at a later date?'. Here a direct link can be made with 'value proposition that may change over time'

Since administrative and operational activities ask for a substantial and continuous investment in the functioning of a partnership, such a leadership role – by one or a small group of individuals – is crucial and needs to be assumed by one responsible leader.

This leader also needs to **provide a clear vision and overview of actions where the partnership is heading since it needs to be convincing for so many different actors (categories) involved.**

Even more, the link with founders and the connection of the partnership with others outside the partnership **further legitimize the necessity of a representative leader.** Consequently, the process of how this leader is selected and appreciated by the different actors is important to consider. Generally, as observed, the organization is selected which is most engaged in the creation of the initiative. In the cases of PMM and Foodwest, a team has been created that is dedicated to the partnership's ambitions and operations. **Furthermore, important points of vigilance arise concerning communication – from leader to different actors and vice versa – and the relationship between the leading organization and the other partners.** A key question is to what extent partners can influence the decision-making process or change the leadership structure itself, if necessary. If not well addressed within the network of actors representing the different categories of functioning (public administration, academic sector, business, ...) – and laid down in the partnership's binding program documents – the democracy of the governance model is at stake as well as a lasting fair involvement of all actors. The MC case here reveals interesting insights. Concerning a partnership focusing on sustainability outcomes, and, hence, being flexible, adaptive, and exemplary, this issue is fundamental and needs full consideration.

Observation 3: Funding is dependent on the legal status of the partnership (III)

Partnerships, whatever their size and scale, have a big impact on the economy or a specific territory. The four cases have received public funding, at least during their creation phase. Foodwest, being a private company, is now nearly 100% self-financed by selling its services while respecting the objectives stated by the owners/members. Hence, it became quite independent in its decision-making process. PMM, also serving the private sector next to other categories, received most of its funds from the regions. The reason is that it is operating as an association with a non-profit status, i.e. not selling its services. Even if they could do it on some occasions, it is not their objective. BIOEAST and MC are not independent structures but are running thanks to an agreement between involved organizations. They cannot sell their services and are obliged to seek external funds. This is stressed as a barrier to keeping the organization's administration running smoothly. The acquisition sum depends on their scales of operations. BIOEAST has been and is still seeking European funds for projects. MC is partly financed by the partners who signed the MOU (e.g. city of Milan, Cariplo Foundation) and via other private sponsorships.

➔ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

In all interviews, the availability of funds has been highlighted as a challenging issue. Seeking new funds is a time-consuming activity and each partnership has its strategy on how to get them. **Almost every partnership, except BIOEAST, benefitted from a dedicated fund related to the partnerships' specific context**¹⁰. This allowed launching the partnership. Thereafter, strategies had to be adapted to become autonomous while fulfilling (new) objectives. Then, other funders stepped in. Foodwest was the only case in which a lack of external funds didn't cause difficulties. Their business model was built on selling their services; public funds only served as accelerators. The other three cases are not selling services; their objectives were to create new, common, projects. PMM had briefly experienced selling some services, but it took too much time to develop these new activities. Yet, since regional funds continue to decrease, it may become a necessity to sell services soon. Partnerships that have been created within a well-defined, initially mainly public framework (like the Milan Food Pack with its MOU) seem to be more economically stable. They consist of a larger network and include solid funders at the core of their governance model. Starting a partnership from scratch without having other initial financial support than the motivation of partners appeared as delicate and fragile. Interviews conducted within the BIOEAST case highlighted how slow the initiative was developing without sufficient financial back-up. The unavailability of financial means was here considered a serious drawback or barrier. European project funding served to boost the initial development but could not be used for its daily functioning.

Finally, funding sources depend both on the objective of the partnership and its initial context. **Mixing different funding sources, and not only relying on public funds, which could fluctuate due to political movements, seems to be a factor of success for a resilient partnership.**

Observation 4: The decision-making process is handled by a small team, governed by a board of partner representatives, and (in)formal processes are suggested to be clearly defined (IV)

¹⁰ It is worth mentioning that the work of the BIOEAST initiative has been supported from 2019 to 2023 by the Horizon 2020 project **Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European countries: BIOEASTsUP**, led by the Polish Institute of Cultivation, Fertilisation and Soil Science. For further reading, please consult: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862699>. Currently, the project, that is supporting this initiative, is **HE Boost4BIOEAST - BOOSTing the bioeconomy transformation FOR (4) the BIOEAST region** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101133398>

All final decision-making processes – the ones that deal with the general strategy or administration of the partnership – are led by a small team, and presided by a specific board. The actors acting on the board mainly originate from the partners involved in the creation of the initiative. Thereafter, it depends on their willingness to open the board to other partners' representatives. In the cases of PMM and MC, partners' representatives and partners are involved in the decision-making process right from the start of the initiative. For BIOEAST and Foodwest, other partner representatives are consulted by the board. Their boards are composed of one type of actor (respectively ministries for BIOEAST and (business) managers for Foodwest) and have final decision power.

→ **Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships**

The interviews showed **3 different ways of consulting and implicating partners to decide on actions within the partnership**; these are going from the less inclusive to the most inclusive actions:

- **Using outputs of the work done by the partners for expert advice**, extra data (BIOEAST)
- **Involving partner's representatives that have been elected before** by each partner from the different sectors (PMM, Foodwest)
- **Favoring informality** in exchanges to collect partners' feelings and transfer these to the board (Foodwest, PMM) or to decide on daily, on-the-ground actions (MC)

Based on our four in-depth case studies, it is hard to conclude if formal decision-making processes and elections are more – or less – inclusive than those based on informal discussions and agreements. Many of the PMM's interviewees expressed their appreciation of the election process's efficiency which is considered equalitarian and irrevocable. However, it implies that representatives should be able to voice their sector correctly. Informality allows us to collect directly some perceptions and feelings that could not always be voiced during formal open meetings. It may even create tensions with a single partner. Informal decision-making is especially practical for on-the-ground actions that do not necessarily require a collective decision. Nevertheless, too much informality could lead to a loss of global concertation and drifting away from common objectives; this has been especially noticed by some interviewees of MC.

Both ways of communication have their pros and cons and are proposed to be used together. It is what the four partnerships are doing and they are aware of the pros and cons. Since this last point could lead to miscommunications and tensions, **it is thus important to define where formal processes are necessary, where informal exchanges are favorable, and, how it may accelerate or slow down activities**. Transparency in the articulation of recommendations is in all cases primordial because uncomfortable feelings of what takes place behind the scenes build mistrust.

Annexe 4: Example of a ‘game’ template used for the analysis of the 52 cases (see FOODPathS Deliverable D2.1 for an overview of all cases)

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country **Pôle Mer Méditerranée/France**
 One or two key features: **Innovation platform**
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): **running**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Launched in 2000 by the Marine & Submarine Network to stimulate collaboration between smalls and big firms, research actors around one precise theme. Pole Mer Méditerranée also interacts with his brother site Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique in order to exchange their skills and experiences.

Which ambitions and objectives: The main objective is to sustainably develop blue economy, including fisheries, through innovation. It is first created to stimulate competitiveness but sustainability is on top of the agenda.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Implemented together with research centres (such as Ifremer, Marseille Oceanology Centre) and regional firms. Public actors have been integrated in the partnership after having been labelled “Pôle de compétitivité”.

What external input and output: call for regional sustainable projects via public funds, services for supporting firms growth.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Région Sud	Small firms, groups	Regional economic development projects	Calling for projects	Market laws, language (French) Support Research and development projects	Financing sustainability-oriented projects	2000 : creation of Toulon Var Technologies
Blue Economy	Research centre	Services for enhancing businesses' growth	Supporting regional blue economy business		Supporting the development of small regional business	2005 : labelled “pôle de compétitivité”
	Ecosystem (professional associations, banks, consultants...)				Financial sustainability of the region via innovation and competitiveness	2013 : Pôle PACA become Pôle Méditerranée because of its new international ambitions

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Pôle Mer Med is very close to blue economy actors and is present in many regional projects	Complementary actions to get the results	Kind of cluster that is driven by the Pole Med team	Enhance sustainable blue economy of the French Med regions	Enhance sustainable blue economy around the Mediterranean and at the international scale
Key actors in marine innovation gathered		Pole Med organize a lot of workshops where the actors can meet and exchange		

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

They are present in some key sustainability regional projects, even if there are no direct economic benefits for the actors included. Pole Med have globally a technological vision of the sustainability. They want to be a vitrine of sustainable blue economy at the international levels and get included in various Interreg Med.

Annexe 5: Interview guide; only governance part for the in-depth case study

3. (governance) Who are the members of the network and how do they collaborate?
 - a. Who are the main (public, private, other) actors and partners of the network? How do they work together (contracts, joint investments, mutualized equipment etc.?) What are the drivers and what are the enablers for this collaboration? How are risks, responsibilities, revenues, costs, (if any) shared...?
 - b. Which interactions are crucial between actors to reach this common objective?
 - c. How are decisions taken in the initiative (either formal or informal)? Has this method changed over time? Why/how?
 - d. How are the members committed to the mission?
 - e. How, when and under which conditions do you admit participants in the initiative? Has this method changed over time? How/why?

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